

VALKYRIES

D7.7 Report of the use case: Bulgaria-Greece

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the process of planning, preparation, execution and analysis of results from the Use Case 3 Bulgaria - Greece exercise focused on cross-border interagency reaction in a case of a strong earthquake, floods and pollution of Struma River with a number of victims and first responders involved. A full-scale Multi-Casualty Incident (MCI) simulation was conducted on the Bulgarian Greece border. Affecting victims from both countries and cooperation among first responders. It is important to underline that exercise was planned and implemented particularly to demonstrate and to test the tools proposed by the VALKYRIES project and this was a great achievement of the organisers of the exercise. During the UC3 execution, novel technological tools to reduce voice communications, using various digital tools, and thus reducing the time it takes for victims to be attended and transferred to a hospital, was successfully tested. Besides, the traditional (analog) vs digital triage approach was tested. Last but not least, in the UC3 were demonstrated and tested a Joint Multinational First Responders Training Kit and CIMIC course and training for volunteers.

This document describes the results from the harmonisation opportunities identified in the WP4, WP5 and WP6 that have been tested in the UC3.

According to the evaluations of the first responders from Bulgaria and Greece participating in exercise, the UC3 was a great success and the presented VALKYRIES solutions were highly appreciated.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

The main goal of the VALKYRIES project is to identify the current state of technological solutions, operative procedures, collaboration, education and training opportunities provided to European first responders. Besides, the Project aims to identify capability gaps and harmonisation opportunities at the European level. The project consortium proposes a number of pre-standardization and harmonization activities that would enable First Responders (FRs) to operate successfully in Multi-Casualty Cross-border incidents (MCI). These harmonization proposals are implemented on a platform as reference integration named SIGRUN. The validity of these proposals was tested and demonstrated in the use case 3 (UC3).

In order to prepare and implement the exercises, a standardized process was agreed between the VALKYRIES partners, and all the necessary steps were captured in a document named EXSPEC (Exercise Specification). This was the crucial document for the preparation and implementation of the UCs. The goal of this document was to summarize and prepare all the information related to demonstrations of stated UCs and necessary to implement them in effective manner with aim to present VALKYRIES elements on a relatively simple case before moving on to an extensive deployment.

3.2. Justification

During the different stages of the VALKYRIES project implementation, capability gaps and needs of the end-users in cross-border MCI were analysed and a set of requirements was formulated. Afterwards, different technological tools, systems and equipment, as well as operational procedures and common training and education system were suggested. Later, opportunities for harmonisation and standardisation of the technological solutions, operative procedures, education, training and collaboration among FRs were developed. The results of this process are subject to evaluation and validation also through the USs, including UC3. The technological tools and opportunities tested are described in more detail in chapter 9.

3.3. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.7_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (Detailed implementation plan of UC3, Annex B.
REQ_BASE_T7.7_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (D3.4)
REQ_BASE_T7.7_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (D2.1)
REQ_BASE_T7.7_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-5	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (Organised two

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK- OBJ-7			planning conferences between Bulgarian and Greek partners in DEC 2022 and in APR 2023) and two field visits of the Main Coordination Team (MCT) from the Bulgarian side in the town of Sandanski in NOV 2022 and in FEB 2023 to coordinate UC3 preparation with the local authorities, Fire brigade Department (FBD), Emergency Medical Services (EMS) and the Police Department (PD).
REQ_BASE_T7.7_5	P1	VALK- OBJ-7 VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (organised a joint multinational training for first responders a day before the exercise with the use of VALKYRIES solutions)
REQ_BASE_T7.7_6	P1	VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Partially Achieved because of the withdrawal of the Bulgarian Red Cross (BRC) from the exercise. Provided briefing for the Greek partners on the day of their arrival in Sandanski. Bulgarian FD and PD in Sandanski provided logistics support and escort

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
					of the Greek colleagues.
REQ_BASE_T7.7_7	P1	VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (AREU prepared and demonstrated during the UC3 execution a minimum set of competencies for volunteers to participate in cross-border MCI incidents)
REQ_COM_T7.7_1	P1	VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (The UC3 was planned and implemented in close cooperation between the BDI the Military Medical Academy, Fire Brigade, as well as the partners from Greece - KEMEA and the HRT.)
REQ_COM_T7.7_2	P1	VALK- OBJ-5 VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (D3.4)
REQ_COM_T7.7_3	P1	VALK- OBJ-1 VALK- OBJ-5 VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (Followed the SOPs of the Bulgarian Fire Brigade and developed UC3 Implementation Plan)
REQ_COM_T7.7_4	P1	VALK- OBJ-7 VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	REQUIRED	Achieved (A plan for CIMIC was prepared in advance.)
REQ_COM_T7.7_5	P2	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	OPTIONAL	Achieved (The WP6 E&T kit was tested during the exercise.)
REQ_COM_T7.7_6	P1	VALK- OBJ-7	D7.7	RECOMMENDED	Partially Achieved (country briefings/factsheets

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK- OBJ-9			were presented to the Greek partners upon arrival in Sandanski); logistics support and escort from the border provided
REQ_COM_T7.7_7	P2	VALK- OBJ-7 VALK- OBJ-9	D7.7	RECOMMENDED	Achieved (Briefing for volunteers was presented by AREU regarding the minimum competences to participate in cross-border MCI)

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix T7.7

4. Demonstration specification

4.2. References

- Project VALKYRIES, Number: 101020676 — Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters (Description of Action)
- Dx.x – related deliverables (UC descriptions, technical solutions descriptions).
 - D7.1 Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology.
 - D7.2 Datasets Management and Benchmarking.
 - D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation.
 - D7.4 Reference Integration and lessons learned.

4.3. General data

The outcomes of technological, procedural and collaborative streams were covered in the VALKYRIES reference integrated platform (SIGRUN), evaluation and demonstration actions. Activity is based on project Task 7.7 and covers the planning, implementation, integration, executing, analysis and reporting activities concerning the demonstration scenario: cross-border response to strong earthquake close to the Bulgarian-Greece border, heavy floods and leak of dangerous chemicals in Struma River on the border between Bulgaria and Greece.

5. Overall requirements

5.2. General framework

The Use case 3 (UC3) refers to a cross-border emergency intervention in case of an Earthquake incident involving Bulgaria and Greece. It happened in Southwestern Bulgaria between the towns of Sandanski and Petrich with the epicentre at 16 kilometres from the border. A strong earthquake with a magnitude of 6.9 on the Richter scale caused a series of humanitarian crises and industrial accidents threatening the lives of the population in the Bulgarian-Greek border area.

The earthquake resulted in a Multi Casualty Incident (MCI) with victims and injured people on both sides of the border. More than 20 victims are reported on the Bulgarian side and there are many injured people in the worst affected municipalities. The number of victims and injured people is expected to increase. In addition to the consequences of the earthquake, large amounts of precipitation due to heavy rainfalls lasting for several days have resulted in substantial floods.

Besides, there is confirmed information about cracks in the wall of the Logodazh dam, which is in the proximity of the worst affected by the earthquake areas. This significantly increased the danger of floods. Moreover, there is a leakage of acrylonitrile and ammonia in Struma River because of a reservoir failure at a polymer plant near the town of Petrich and a disruption in the operation of cold storage for vegetables. Telecommunications are seriously disrupted due to the earthquake.

Finally, heavy traffic is observed in the border area because of thousands of citizens of Greece and North Macedonia vacationing in the region trying to leave the affected areas.

The MCI and the major damages are on the Bulgarian territory, but the earthquake/flood and the leakage of chemicals affects also Greek territory and the population. Several Bulgarian first responder units are deployed to the affected area for the identification of victims and providing health assistance to the casualties. Collaboration and coordination among different first responder teams from Bulgaria and Greece are needed.

The following table from D2.3 presents the actors of the UC3 and the tools to be used.

Operational Actors	Technological Artifacts
National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, PCs and connection to the internet.
National Centre of Emergency Call 112, Bulgaria	112 Terminal and emergency call management system, PCs and connection to the internet, emergency management software.
Bulgarian Military Medical Academy triage team	Portable radios and mobile phones; TETRA
Bulgarian Fire Brigade	Portable radios and mobile phones; TETRA
Bulgarian Police	Portable radios and mobile phones; TETRA
Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service (Sandanski and Petrich hospital)	Portable radios and mobile phones; TETRA

Operational Actors	Technological Artifacts
Political Liaison	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Civil Protection	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Coordination Centre 112 Greece	112 Terminal and emergency call management system, PCs and connection to the internet, emergency management software.
Hellenic Rescue Team	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Hellenic Fire Brigade	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Hellenic National Centre for Emergency Assistance	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, PCs and connection to the internet.
Hellenic Earthquake Planning and Protection Organization (EPPO).	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, PCs and connection to the internet.
Citizens	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, social media
Victims	User Terminal (Mobile phones)
Hospitals	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, APP_MONITOR
Ambulance	GLOBAL_COP

Table 2 – UC3 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)

5.3. Relation to other demonstrations

The Demonstration “Joint Cross-border Multi Casualty Incident Response 2023” represents UC3, and it is one of the four different demonstrations within the project. Not all VALKYRIES elements had been tested in this demonstration. Overlapping or missing parts were subject to subsequent assessment and evaluation.

6. Demonstration aims and objectives

6.2. Demonstration aim

To validate and evaluate the VALKYRIES technological solutions, innovative operative procedures, as well as collaboration, education and training opportunities for first responders in case of cross-border multi casualty incidents as described in D7.3 [3].

6.3. Demonstration objective

- EO1: To provide an extensive presentation of VALKYRIES solutions to first responders from Bulgaria and Greece and to train them jointly to use these instruments in the exercise.
- EO2: To provide participating first responders with outcomes of VALKYRIES project. To organize, conduct and evaluate joint multinational cross-border exercise of first responders using the tools and products of the VALKYRIES project according to the scenario.
- EO3: To verify VALKYRIES harmonization opportunities identified in the WP4 (technologies), WP5 (operative procedures) and WP6 (collaboration, education and training) as a tool of improvement of end user's capabilities.
- EO4: To collect data and to compare the results from triage of victims done in the traditional way and using VALKYRIES applications for digitalizing triage process.
- EO5: To get feedback from the first responders regarding the quality and usefulness of SIGRUN for management of cross-border MCI, as well as their satisfaction with the use of the VALKYRIES products related to innovative operative procedures, collaboration, education and training tools.
- EO6: To disseminate the project outputs and support exploitation of the project results among first responders' organisations.

6.4. Testing objectives

- TO1: To assess the digitisation tools proposed by the VALKYRIES project to reduce the time spent on voice communications.
- TO2: To assess the accuracy of an application to digitalize triage process to classify correctly casualties according to the severity of their injuries.
- TO3: To compare the time and performance of an "analogue/traditional" versus a "digital" triage solution.
- TO4: To evaluate the impact on a command and control of a digital decision support solution.
- TO4: To evaluate the satisfaction of end users with the Joint multinational training kit for first responders, CIMIC training course and formulated minimum set of competencies of volunteers in cross-border MCI.

7. Operational scenario description

A strong earthquake caused a disaster and industrial accident threatening the lives of the population in the Bulgarian-Greek border area. The incident happened in South-western Bulgaria between the towns of Sandanski and Petrich with the epicentre at 16 kilometres from the Bulgarian-Greek border. The wall of the Logodazh Dam, which is located 60 km. from the epicentre of the earthquake, is seriously damaged generating high risks of heavy floods. More than 20 victims are reported on the Bulgarian side and there are many injured people in the most affected municipalities. Besides, more than 20 victims are reported on the Greek side. The number of injured people is expected to increase in the process of search and rescue operations. Several different first response intervention units must be deployed. Effective cross-border and inter-agency cooperation and harmonized procedures for cooperation are needed, especially in view of the cross-border threat. Specific equipment is required, as well.

Time of emergency call: 5:43 AM

The National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences identified an earthquake with a magnitude of 6.9 on the Richter scale with the epicentre in the area between the towns of Petrich and Sandanski (Bulgaria).

There are multiple calls to the emergency number "112". From "112" or The National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences the calls are redirected to National Operations Centre of the Fire department, the Regional Operations Centre in Blagoevgrad, the Police department and the Emergency ambulance service. When the Regional Centre received the call, they sent out teams from the local Fire departments in city of Sandanski and Petrich, which are closest to the epicentre. The main task of the first teams is to evaluate the situation.

There is a great number of affected people. More than 45 victims are reported on both the Bulgarian and Greek sides of the border and there are many injured people in the worst affected municipalities. The number of the injured and victims is expected to increase. The earthquake caused the damage of a reservoir and the leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile at a polymer plant in the town of Petrich which has been reported to emergency number 112.

At the same time, because of heavy rainfall during the last 10 days, there have been significant spills and floods along the Struma and Mesta rivers on the Bulgarian territory. The wall of the Logodazh Dam, which is located at 60 km. from the epicentre of the earthquake, is seriously destroyed generating high risks of heavy floods.

The National Centre of Emergency Call "112" operator on duty informs the National Operating Centre and the Regional Operating Centre of the Fire department, the Police Call Centre and the emergency centre.

The Regional Operating Centre informs the Fire department in Sandanski, the local police department and emergency teams. Following the existing operative procedures, fire trucks of the fire department in the town of Sandanski are taken outside the garages. The Duty officer at the Regional Operating Centre informs the Director of the Regional Fire Department about the situation and reports to the National Operating Centre for the taken actions.

The Director of Regional Fire Department implements the Crisis, Emergency and Disaster Response Plan in the earthquake and floods section. The Regional Operating Centre notifies all personnel of the Fire Department in Sandanski, the Specialized Operational Activities Team and

the Operational Headquarters of the Directorate. The Regional Operating Centre orders additional forces and resources to go to the accidents and reports to the National Operating Centre for the taken actions.

The Mayor of Sandanski municipality gave the order to call the members of the Regional Headquarters and to activate the Disaster Recovery Plan in the earthquake section. The Mayor acts as the Chief of Staff while for operational management, the role is played by the representative of the Fire department.

The Operational Headquarters (OHQ) of the Regional Directorate of the General Directorate "Fire Safety and protection of Population" (FSPP) of the Ministry of Interior (Mol) is dispatched on site, takes over the leadership and, if necessary, and calls representatives of the other first responder units to its composition.

The OHQ assesses the situation and it is deployed to provide additional forces and capabilities from the emergency teams, Police Department (PD), Voluntary Formations (VF) from Sandanski, and military formations for the establishment of triage points and transport of the injured to a hospital. The OHQ provides a corridor for the movement of fire and rescue equipment to the area of the accident and back, cordoning off the area and ensuring a permeable regime in the accident site and the safety of the headquarters, keeps a record of the number and nationality of the victims.

The OHQ requires a helicopter crew from the military formation 32040 - Krumovo, to carry out reconnaissance and to assess the situation in the area. The OHQ requires from the Ministry of Health construction of the Field centres for reception, medical triage by a doctor specializing in emergency medicine, treatment and preparation of the injured for transport and evacuation from the area. The Field centres support the implementation of first psychological support and primary collection of information about the victims.

The Mayor of Sandanski municipality receives a request from the Director of the Regional Fire Department (FD) for a helicopter from the Operational Headquarters. The Mayor of Sandanski municipality sends a request to the Ministry of Defence/Chief of Defence for providing a helicopter from the military formation 32040 - Krumovo to conduct a reconnaissance operation.

The crew of the helicopter from the military formation 32040 - Krumovo was prepared to conduct a search for victims using specialized equipment for searching and locating people through a broadcast signal from mobile cellular receivers and thermal cameras. Due to bad weather conditions, the flight was cancelled. The observation was done only by drones.

The Bulgarian authorities are in contact with the counterparts in Greece. This is not an official way of contact, yet only personal-based.

Time after the intervention of the first aid responders: 06:00 AM

After the reconnaissance is done, many casualties were reported and collapsed buildings, as well as leakage of toxic substances in the Sruma River from the polymer plant in the town of Petrich.

Forces and capabilities of the General Directorate (GD) "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Ministry of Interior (Mol) of the Republic of Bulgaria is deployed. The Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service is also deployed, as well as regional units from the Bulgarian Police. It is expected a Military CBRN unit to arrive soon. The Bulgarian border police are undertaking activities to ease up on the return of the citizens of Greece and the North Macedonia in their home countries.

All the services act according to the existing operating procedures. Search and rescue operations for victims of the earthquake and extinguishing local outbreaks begin to take place.

EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) has not been activated so far. Upon notification of the Greek authorities (even through personal contact), Greek authorities are in alert to act when asked and the Greek 112 issues mass alerts to citizens living close the border (on the Greek side). The telephone connection, including the connection of the mobile operators, has been disrupted, which makes communication in the area difficult. A large part of the water supply network in the epicentre of the earthquake was also destroyed.

In coordination with the Greek authorities, the Bulgarian counterparts send a support request. The General Secretary of Civil Protection (GSCP) in Greece is informed and assessing the situation. At the same time, the Hellenic GSCP requests Rescue NGOs to provide a readiness level of support and time for mobilisation.

The Hellenic Rescue Team (HRT) states their availability for immediate mobilisation and arrival time on site within 2 hours with a small team for the first phase (assessment and SAR). It also provides backup teams ready to deploy on-site at the next phase, as the HRT's HQ is located only 150 km away (simulated action).

By the time HRT units are on the field, and are registered at the local Base of Operation. They are assigned to the working groups either for SAR activities or at the Command-and-Control Post.

Time after the intervention of the first aid responders: 06:45 AM

A request has been received between the municipalities on both sides of the border for the inclusion in the rescue operations of first aid teams from the Republic of Greece.

The Operational Headquarters of the Hellenic Municipality is deployed near the Bulgarian-Greece border (simulated).

Teams from the Hellenic Republic arrive by bilateral Bulgaria – Greece agreement or standard operating procedures (simulated).

First aid teams from Greece come to the OHQ, who is located in the city of Sandanski. They are included in the actions of rescue and extraction of the injured people from the buildings, as well as first medical aid and psychological support of the injured, triage, first medical aid and preparation for transportation to medical facilities.

A Field Triage Station was established with adequate safety measures. Information and a Common Operational Picture are shared through the SIGRUN platform between the OHQs of Bulgaria and Greece (simulated).

Extraction of victims from the Struma River, limitation of flooded areas and stop the spill of hazardous chemicals. Construction of dikes in the flooded areas to prevent the scale of the flood. Limiting the spill of hazardous substances/ the reason is chemical leak in the river from the treatment of the nearby agriculture fields/ in the Struma River.

Rescuing or evacuating people and movable property from flooded areas. Construction of a Field centre for rescue, first medical aid and psychological support of the injured.

Distribution of the injured (triage), first medical aid for the wounded and probably affected people from the agricultural chemicals, preparation for transportation to medical facilities. Setting up a casualty triage station.

A Field Triage Station is established with adequate safety measures.

The OHQ checks the possibility of attracting unmanned aerial vehicles (drones) for reconnaissance and coordination of forces by means of video broadcasting in the area.

It is required to mobilize the drones available in FD.

Information and a Common Operational Picture are shared through the SIGRUN platform between the OHQs of Bulgaria and Greece (simulated).

Extraction the victims from collapsed hostel where foreign country citizens are accommodated. The firefighters and rescue team provide an initial triage of the victims and first aid is given.

Those who need an evacuation and hospitalization are transported by ambulance.

NOTICE: For the needs of the project the premises of the municipality of Sandanski were used for demonstration (Sports hall).

Map of the affected area: Towns of Blagoevgrad (District centre), Sandanski and Petrich that are most affected areas. The epicentre of the earthquake is marked with a red dot between the villages Rupite and Novo Delchevo.

Figure 1 - The area of UC3 execution

Overall Description

The earthquake caused the damage of a reservoir and the leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile at a polymer plant in the town of Petrich. In addition, the integrity of the refrigeration system in vegetable refrigerated warehouses has been disrupted, due to large amounts of ammonia continue to leak. At the same time, because of heavy rainfall during the last 10 days, there have been significant spills and floods along the Struma and Mesta rivers on the Bulgarian territory.

Almost all settlements in the regions along the two rivers are affected. The wall of the Logodazh Dam, which is located at 60 km. from the epicentre of the earthquake, is seriously destroyed generating high risks of heavy floods. The telephone connection, including the connection of the mobile operators, has been disrupted, which makes communication in the area and requests for support from neighbouring countries (including Greece) and EUCPM difficult. A large part of the water supply network in the epicentre of the earthquake was destroyed.

The resulting panic among the population of the larger affected settlements such as the towns of Kresna, Sandanski and Melnik has led to the concentration of cars and trucks on their entry and exit roads and hinders the traffic. Extremely busy traffic is observed on the main road E-79 in the direction of the border checkpoint with Greece "Kulata-Promachonas" and the national road III-106 in the direction of the border checkpoint with Northern Macedonia "Logodazh" (Former "Stanke Lisichkovo"). This is a result of the hundreds of citizens of the Hellenic Republic and the Republic of Northern Macedonia leaving the disaster area, vacationing in Sandanski, Melnik and other resorts in the south-western part of the Republic of Bulgaria.

Own Operatives

Ambulances from the towns of Blagoevgrad, Sandanski/Petrich and the Military Medical Academy in Sofia have been mobilized. The regional units of the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population", the regional directorate of the Bulgarian Police in Blagoevgrad, Sandanski and Petrich, as well as the Military CBRN unit have been activated.

The Bulgarian mayors of the towns of Blagoevgrad, Sandanski, Petrich and the Regional Governors of Blagoevgrad and Sofia District are informed, and they prepare to implement the plans of the Regional Disaster Risk Reduction Councils. The Voluntary formations, established at municipal level that are under the direct authority of the mayors of the affected municipalities, and which are an integral part of the unified rescue system are activated.

It is expected representatives of the Hellenic Fire Brigade to provide support to the Bulgarian authorities.

The Disaster Risk Reduction Council at the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria is informed about the emerging disaster situation and assistance at national level is requested by the local authorities. A specialized disaster medicine team from the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy is also deployed.

Co-operating and neutral actors (this is only possibility – they will not be included in the Ex.)

Military unit – CBRN one must be considered. There is a leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile and ammonia in Struma River that need specialized expertise. Universities and institutes in Blagoevgrad, Sofia, as well as Greek partners – chemical related faculties/departments, respectively their laboratories might be used for analysis if requested.

Coordinator's Assumptions

The disaster response action is coordinated by the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Mol in close cooperation with the Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service, the local authorities, police, military CBRN unit and the Greek counterparts.

Limitations and constraints

Coordination with Greek counterparts is not possible immediately. A bilateral agreement between Bulgaria and Greece has not been activated yet.

Suitable channels for information exchange are missing, as well.

A Common Alert Protocol needs to be in place.

HRT not allowed to operate in there is pollution of water.

Tactical end-states and objectives

The end-state is achieved, when large-scale damage of the wall of the Logodazh Dam is prevented, the results from the floods are under control, the leak of chemicals is identified, the toxicity of the water in Struma and Mesta rivers - threatening level and all reported injuries are managed (threatened or hospitalized).

Execution

First Aid is provided by responders coming as first on the place from the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Mol, the Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service and the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy to save lives and minimize damage to health. Subsequently and immediately after arrival of ambulances and paramedics specialized care will be provided (triage, treatment, transport to hospital if necessary and related admission of patients) in the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy and regional hospitals in Blagoevgrad, Sandanski and Petrich.

As this is a disaster including a chemicals linkage incident, zoning must be carried out, based on first measurements, detection and threat identification. The CBRN incident Standard Operative Procedures (SOP) was applied. The first responders had to work in Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). Contamination of victims must be taken into consideration (treatment, transport, hospitalization, etc.)

Tasks and business processes

1. Receiving an emergency call to number 112;
2. Activation of forces, deployment of the first responder's units;
3. Evaluation of the situation by the GD "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Bulgarian Mol on site and reporting through the national Command and Control (C2) system, application of related SOPs;
4. In this case it is obvious that this is MCI – so it means activation of more forces and resources (ambulances, specialized CBRN teams – civil protection, police, military unit, etc.);
5. Preparation for admission of injuries in the hospitals;
6. Preparing for multi-regional response actions (activation of forces and recourses on national level, gathering the members of the Regional Headquarters and activating the Disaster Recovery Plan in the earthquake section, considering request for help from Greek counterparts and other bordering countries, as well as on EU level based on the EUCPM).

8. Concept of the exercise (demonstration)

8.1. Concept of the demonstration

The planning for the UC3 execution started well in advance more than six months before the day D. The plan was to have at least two meetings between Bulgarian and Greek VALKYRIES partners to coordinate the activities and several on-site meetings of the Main Coordination Team (MCT) from the BDI on the Bulgarian side with the local authorities, Fire brigade, Police and Non-Governmental Organizations from Blagoevgrad and the town of Sandanski.

8.2. Phase I – Preparation

Activity	Date	Participants
Technical preparation on site	1 week before D	BDI & Technical partners
Coordination with the representatives of the Sandanski municipality	DEC 2022	BDI & the Mayor of Sandanski municipality
Meetings of the local authorities, end-users and the Main Coordination Team (MCT) from BDI	DEC 2022 FEB 2023 JUN 2023	MCT, end-users, Technical partners owners of the tools
Initial Joint Bulgarian – Greek workshop to discuss the planning and execution of the UCs in Starosel, Bulgaria	DEC 2022	BDI, MCT, end-users, KEMEA, HRT, ARATOS
Training for the use of the VALKYRIES new tools	DEC 2022 APR 2023 JUN 2023	MCT, players, trainers, Technical partners owners of the tools
Event registration	One month before D	All participants
Final reconnaissance of the MCT meeting on the spot	1 month before D	MCT
Initial reconnaissance meeting on the spot	6 months before D	MCT
Procurement of materials for Ex	till 1 month before D	MCT
Confirmation of venues (site, hotel, transport, catering...), logistic letter to all participants, etc.	5 months before D	MCT
Invitation letters for policy-makers	4 months before D	MCT
List of participants	1 month before D	MCT
Coordination meetings with local authorities	several	MCT
Final planning conference for execution of UC3 and preliminary training for the use of VALKYRIES tools	APR 2023	BDI, MCT, end-users, KEMEA, HRT, ARATOS (on-site), INDRA, TASSICA, PARTICLE (online)

Table 3 – UC3 Technical and logistics planning

8.3. Phase II – Shaping – Technology and participants (intervention) preparation

PLAYERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Directorate “Fire safety and Protection of Population”, Bulgarian Mol, Deputy Director, Director of Blagoevgrad District and the representative of the FD of the town of Sandanski; (Very active role and real contribution to the success of the UC3 execution); • National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography, Bulgarian Academy of Science (Simulated role); • National Centre of Emergency Call 112 (Simulated role); • Military medical academy team (Real actor; one ambulance team and medical cadets, ambulance and bus); • Bulgarian Emergency ambulance services (Sandanski/Petrich) (Real actors at least one local hospital/ambulance service); • Bulgarian military unit (CBRN) (Real actor); • Regional Police department in Sandanski) Real actor; • Political Liaison (Simulated role); • Hellenic Civil Protection authorities (Real actors); one person from the Self Directorate of Civil Protection of the Central Macedonia Region; • Bulgarian armed forces (a helicopter and crew) (Real actors, planned but not executed because of the the bad weather conditions); • Hellenic Rescue Team (Real actors); • Hellenic Fire Brigade (Real actors; liaison officer), seven in total: the liaison officer from the Fire Service Command of the Prefecture of Thessaloniki, three persons from the specialised unit for disaster management of Thessaloniki and three persons from the respective unit of Komotini; • Hellenic National Centre for Emergency Assistance (EKAB) (Real actors), six persons in total, one from the Specialised Unit for Disaster Medicine of Athens and five from the respective Unit of Kavala; • Citizens (Real actors/cadets); • Victims (Real actors/cadets); • Volunteers from the municipality of Sandanski and the Bulgarian Red Cross (BRC) Blagoevgrad (Real actors).
SOLUTION PROVIDERS (technical partners)	INDRA TASSICA PARTICLE
SOLUTIONS USED IN THE UC.	<p>Tested and demonstrated applications and solutions in UC3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SIGRUN implementation reference; - iSAFETY; - GLOBAL COP; - Application for digitalizing triage process; - TASSICA TB bracelets; - TASSICA 3 triage cards; - National triage cards.

	Additional tools used to run and to set-up the UC3 scenarios: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Victims' simulators; - Ambulance / vehicles /assets simulators (routes and status); - Demo scenario set-up; - Events / Tasks simulators.
OBSERVERS AND EVALUATORS	INDRA TASSICA PARTICLE AREU SUMMA USN

Table 4 – UC3 Main players and solution providers

For the purposes of UC3 in the part of flooding, a Hydrometeorological model of Logodazh River and the Dam was developed by a team from the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences to demonstrate and visualize the effect of the flood on the Bulgarian and Greece territories (Annex M).

MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION TEAMS	
Exercise director	Nikiolai Stoianov, BDI
Exercise deputy director	Yantsislav Yanakiev
Scenario planners	Valeri Ivanov, BDI and John Tsaloukidis, KEMEA, Dimitrios Iliadis
Evaluation leaders	Maya Bozhilova, BDI and Danai Kazantzidou-Firtinidou, KEMEA
Logistic and technical coordinator	Kostadin Kostadinov, BDI
End-users' coordinator	Valeri Ivanov, BDI
Exercise safety officer	Valeri Ivanov, BDI
Technical support (computers, printers, internet, communications, etc.)	Pencho Vasilev, BDI Pavlina Nikolova, BDI Borisl Hristov, BDI

Table 5 – UC3 Management and coordination teams

8.4. Phase III – Conduct live exercise

A detailed UC3 implementation plan was developed and coordinated between the Bulgarian and Greek partners responsible for the exercise execution. The plan defines the number of participants, events and expected activities from the main players, real and operational time, command and control chain, and agenda for the execution of the UC3 (Annex B).

The following Information flows were derived for UC3:

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
1. BG ALERT	Communication of the incident detection from the National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography of the Bulgarian Academy of Science.
2. BG COMMAND POST - BG Raises alert	Reports credible incident alerts received to the proper command centre.

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
3. BG Dispatch	Data required to deploy a local Command post, in response to a confirmed incident
4. Situational awareness	Report Incident victims and medical situation, data received
5. BG Incident reported	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (BG)
6. BG Public order and humanitarian assistance	Citizen ID data, status, agency in charge, instructions, destination
7. BG Public warning	Agency in charge, instructions, means
8. BG Victim data	Victim ID data, health data, privacy authorization
9. BG First responder data	FR position, ID, status
10. BG-GR Reference alert	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents
11. GR Incident reported	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents
12. BG-GR Political coordination	Countries authorization and political agreements
13. GR COMMAND POST - GR Raises alert	Reports credible incident alerts received to the proper command centre.
14. GR Public warning	Agency in charge, instructions, means
15. GR Dispatch	Data required to deploy a local Command post, in response to a confirmed incident
16. Situational awareness	Report Incident victims and medical situation, data received
17. GR Public order and humanitarian assistance	Citizen ID data, status, agency in charge, instructions, destination
18. GR Victim data	Victim ID data, health data, privacy authorization
19. GR First responder data	FR position, ID, status
20. BG-GR Dispatch victim to Hospital	Ambulance ID, service ID, Destination, Victim registration ID
21. BG-GR Report victim data	Ambulance position, ETA, victims ID, victims incident origin
22. BG-GR Ambulance data	Victim ID; victim health data

Table 6 - UC3 Information Flows (Source D2.3)

The following interaction scheme represents the actions and capabilities that have been implemented in UC3.

Figure 2 - UC3: Interaction Diagram on the side of Bulgaria and Greece

The following Command and Control Chain has been established during the UC3 Exercise in Sandanski.

Figure 3 - UC3: Command and Control Chain

8.5. Phase IV – Evaluation (Brief description of the approach (algorithm and methodology) for validation and testing of the VALKYRIES results)

The process of evaluation and validation of the VALKYRIES solution in the framework of Use Case 3 follows the methodology and guidelines described in D7.1 [5] and D7.3 [3].

Validation occurs during the execution of the use cases. It is carried out in parallel with data collection to prove the Project outputs. The groundwork for data collection preparation was laid during the planning phase of the use cases, ensuring that evaluation remains a continuous process throughout the use case's duration. In the VALKYRIES context, validation is conducted by end users, comprising first responders and managers, in two distinct stages:

- Validation involves assessing individual solutions used by end users;
- An overarching validation process evaluates the VALKYRIES integrated system as a whole.

As described in the D7.1 [5], the verification of the Harmonisation opportunities, VALKYRIES tools, and the integrated system were conducted and documented in D7.3 [3].

The aim of validation and evaluation of the VALKYRIES solutions within the framework of the Use Case 3 is to test and demonstrate its functionality and usability in order to implement Harmonisation opportunities identified in the WP4, WP5, and WP6 and support first responders for a cross-border emergency intervention in case of an Earthquake incident involving Bulgaria and Greece. Evaluation includes a comprehensive analysis of how well the VALKYRIES solutions align with the expectations of end users and the impact they have on various stakeholders attending the cross-border demonstrations.

The findings and results from the validation and evaluation processes of the harmonisation opportunities implemented, and VALKYRIES tools and integrated system are documented in section 10, section 11, and Annexes H, F, and G of this report.

8.5.1. An approach to validate WP4 Harmonisation opportunities

The harmonization opportunities in WP4 are related to the technology (software) solutions. In this case, validation means that the tool or system being evaluated “behaves” as it should. Therefore, the evaluators followed the functional harmonization opportunities described in the D4.4 document [6] and checked that the evaluation object “behaves” as specified. Testers entered the information just as end users, verified that the software (system) performs the actions it is supposed to do, and checked that their reports were correct.

8.5.2. An approach to validate WP5 Harmonisation opportunities

The outcomes presented to the target audience in the course of the UC3 comprised the outcomes of certification, regulation, standardization, and WP5 harmonization opportunities. Additionally, the outputs also included the potential obtained from integrating the solutions on the SIGRUN platform.

The WP5 results were validated at two stages:

- The days just before the UC3 execution in June 2023 – Training and role-playing exercises of the first responders, C2 managers, etc., on the operational procedures and solutions, specifically proposed by the VALKYRIES Project for the demonstration of WP5 harmonization opportunities were conducted. This training is needed for the adequate level of performance of the participants in the real exercises. At the end of these activities, feedback was collected from the trainees for evaluation.

- In the context of the UC3 execution, a validation of the WP5-related opportunities was implemented within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the VALKYRIES solution two exercises were conducted successively, an exercise was carried out in the usual way and another exercise was carried out with the new operational procedures and solutions proposed by VALKYRIES outcomes. During the exercises, relevant information was gathered in order to evaluate the VALKYRIES solution.

8.5.3. An approach to validate WP6 Harmonisation opportunities

The first WP6 harmonization opportunity is in essence, the technological solution. It was validated as the approach described in section 7.5.1.

The other WP6 opportunities are training kits for a Joint Multinational Training for First Responders, CIMIC course and Minimum Set of Competencies for volunteers. They were validated through presentations and training sessions of the stakeholders one day just before the real UC3 execution. The feedback data using online questionnaire from participants was collected during the debriefing day after UC3 execution in order to analyse the end users' assessments and their satisfaction with the WP6 trainings (Annex C).

9. VALKYRIES Integrated System

Valkyries project produced number of harmonization proposals and developed a platform as reference integration. Validity of selected ones was demonstrated in exercise based on Use Case 3. Brief description of tools used are described in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation - A/1. Annex F”

9.1. Global Technological Schema

The following figure presents the global schema for UC3 with the tools and Command and Control configuration.

Figure 4 - Technological Schema of UC3

For UC3, the two main Headquarters in Bulgaria (Real) and Greece (Simulated in Sandanski) have been established. The Bulgarian Operational Head Quarters (OHQ) was really acting, while the Greek one was simulated. In each of them, the GLOBAL COP application has been deployed to provide the join operational view.

iSafety as a command-and-control tool has been deployed in the Field Operational Centre (FOC) in Bulgaria and from the application the missions have been created and the necessary resources have been assigned for the incident. In the Field Operational Centre, a GLOBAL COP was also deployed with a local view and dashboards with real-time information on the victims were also available.

At the incident site in general, the application for digitalizing triage process integrated in the SIGRUN platform was used to provide real-time data on the victims and triage status.

The tools used for UC3 were iSafety, SIGRUN, GLOBAL COP, Application for Digitalizing Triage Process, Tassica Triage Cards and BlockChain encryption module (this module run on background – practitioners did not realize that).

9.2. Description of Exercises Conducted

For the beginning of the exercise, a signal was given by the National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography at the Bulgarian Academy of Science about a strong earthquake in the area of the city of Sandanski. The Regional Operating Centre informed the Fire Department in Sandanski, local police department and the emergency teams.

The Director of Regional Fire Department (FD) implemented the Crisis, Emergency and Disaster Response Plan in the earthquake and floods section. The Regional Operating Centre notified all personnel of the Fire Department in Sandanski, Specialized Operational Activities Team and the Operational Headquarters of the Directorate.

The Mayor of Sandanski municipality gave an order to gather the members of the Regional Headquarters and to activate the Disaster Recovery Plan in the earthquake section. The Operational Headquarters (OHQ) of the Regional Directorate was dispatched on site, took over the leadership and, if necessary, attracted representatives of the other first responder units to its composition.

The OHQ requested a helicopter crew from military formation 32040 - Krumovo, to carry out reconnaissance and assess the situation in the area and required from the Ministry of Health construction of the Field centres for a reception, sorting by type and degree of disabilities (medical triage) by a doctor specializing in emergency medicine, treatment and preparation of the injured for transport and evacuation from the area.

Due to bad weather conditions the flight of the helicopter was cancelled. The observation was done only by drones.

The Bulgarian authorities were in contact with the counterparts in Greece. This was not an official way of contact, yet only personal-based.

All services took action according to operational procedures. Search and rescue operations for victims of the earthquake and extinguishing local outbreaks have begun.

The EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) has not been activated. Upon notification of the Greek authorities (even through personal contact), Greek authorities were in alert to act when asked and the Greek 112 issued mass alerts to citizens living close to the border (on the Greek side).

In coordination with the Greek authorities, the Bulgarians sent a support request. The General Secretary of Civil Protection (GSCP) in Greece was informed.

The Hellenic Rescue Team (HRT) stated their availability for immediate mobilisation and arrival time on site within 2 hours with a small team for the first phase (assessment and SAR). It also provided backup teams ready to deploy on-site at the next phase, as the HRT's HQ is located only 150 km far (simulated action).

By this time, the HRT Units were on the field, were registered at the local Base of Operation and then assigned to the working groups either for SAR activities or at the Command-and-Control Post.

A request has been received between the two border municipalities on both sides of the border for the inclusion in the rescue operations of first aid teams from the Republic of Greece.

The Operational Headquarters of the Hellenic Municipality were deployed near the Bulgarian-Greece border (simulated). Teams from the Hellenic Republic arrived by bilateral Bulgaria –

Greece agreement or standard operating procedures (simulated). First aid teams from Greece came to the main HQ, who was in city of Sandanski and from there they sent report to the Operational Headquarters for inclusion in the rescue operations.

Fire-fighting actions were taken in the building, which went into rescue and extraction of the injured in the building, and construction of a Field centre for rescue, first medical aid and psychological support of the injured, distribution of the injured (triage), first medical aid, preparation for transportation to medical facilities.

A Field Triage Station was established with adequate safety measures. Information and a Common Operational Picture were shared through the SIGRUN platform between the OHQs of Bulgaria and Greece (simulated). Extraction of victims from the Struma River, limitation of flooded areas and stop the spill of hazardous chemicals.

Distribution of the injured people (triage), first medical aid for the wounded and probably affected people from the agricultural chemicals, preparation for transportation to medical facilities. Setting up a casualty triage station.

Extraction the victims from collapsed hostel where foreign country citizens are accommodated. The firefighters and rescue team provided an initial triage of the victims, and first aid was given

At the end of the exercise, an analysis of the after-action revue of the participating representatives of the various ministries and departments was carried out, and the participants filled out a questionnaire for feedback on the achieved goals of the exercise.

The Bulgarian OHQ was visited by the Deputy Director of the GD “FSPP” of the Ministry of Interior.

Figure 5 – Visit from FSPP in the Bulgarian OHQ

The following images are representative of different moments in the execution of the UC.

Figure 6 – Kick-off of the UC3

Figure 7 – Military medical Academy triage team cooperated with Fire Fighters and Volunteers

Figure 8 – Firefighters from Bulgaria and Greece

Figure 9 – Bulgarian Field Triage Station supported by the partners from TASSICA

Figure 10 – Bulgarian and Greek Participants in the UC3 execution

10. Harmonization opportunities

10.1. WP4 harmonization opportunities

This section provides an explanation of how the harmonisation of the opportunities assessed in UC3 has been carried out. A specific explanation of UC3 is given.

The harmonization opportunities identified in the WP4 that were implemented for UC3 are the following:

- **CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles;**
- **CO.WP4.28. Cross border data trace;**
- **CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges;**
- **CO.WP4.21. Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.**

A detailed description of each opportunity of WP4 is included in D7.3 [3].

10.1.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

This harmonized opportunity was validated in the UC3, addressing the following tests purposes:

- Validate the assets (vehicles) report of their location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed;
- Validate the victims 'report of their location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed;
- Validate the First Responders reported location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed;

The UC3 was performed with the improvements made after UC1 execution.

10.1.2. CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace

For Cross Border data trace, the module "Blockchain logging" of the central system SIGRUN was used as in UC1.

As designed originally in D2.8, this module logs and encrypts all exchanged data and metadata between all federated or external systems attached to SIGRUN system, stamping this logging with a time stamp.

Through this mechanism, specially designed and developed for the Valkyries project following SIGRUN architecture and the Minimum Data Set definitions, the following objectives of the project were ensured:

- Encryption of data, using hash and advanced 256key encryption algorithms provided by the used blockchain network
- Secure access to the system only by users of registered federated systems on SIGRUN
- Compliance with EUs GTBR regulations for personal or sensitive medical data

As for cross border data traceability, as far it was technically impossible to alter or change any logged information, traceability of data was ensured through maximum security and transparency of all operations (also including administration operation of the SIGRUN system, following the internal procedures described in the deliverable D.5.3 SIGRUN Workflow and Risk Assessment Design Document).

The Cross Border factor to validate this functionality was ensured as all such data exchanged between countries during the UC execution were also mapped in the COP of each Authority and the exchanged COP between them in parallel with their logging.

Such Traceability of data, also helps any after incident validation of the performance of the used resources (people or assets) based on robust evidenced data.

During UC3, no differences were traced or reported compared with the results of SIGRUN integration tests or the results of UC1.

10.1.3. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

For UC3, there was a real Field Operational Centre, and the exercise was performed using one day of traditional tools and after provided training, the VALKYRIES Tools.

In UC3 the opportunity to reduce communication times was adjusted to the UC scenario. In the UC3 case, iSafety was deployed as a Command-and-Control (C2) tool in Bulgaria and from there the actions of incident creation, mission creation and vehicle status update were executed.

In parallel, the same actions were being executed with the conventional tools. In this case, radio and voice communications were used and there was no Command-and-Control tool and no integration with the real systems.

iSafety had a liaison operator who was in contact with the operator who managed the resources with the traditional method, and they were introduced in SIGRUN through the iSafety interface in a manual manner.

The same liaison operator entered the Greek data with the information provided by the Greek FRs.

In this case the interactions between FR/Field Operational Centre and HQ in terms of incident creation, mission creation, resource allocation and resource status update are measured.

10.1.4. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

This opportunity has an identical implementation and validation in the three UCs executed in correspondingly Spain-Portugal, Bulgaria-Greece, and Slovakia-Italy. Therefore, to avoid repetition, it is described in "D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation - A/1. Annex F"

10.2. WP5 harmonization opportunities

The opportunities resulting from the WP5 works that have been evaluated in the UC3 demonstrator are the following:

- **CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response:** CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for the response planning, preparedness and execution of Project UCs.
- **CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response:** Two enablers have been evaluated to the UC demonstrator to address this opportunity:
 - CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: Use of unified casualties triage priority coding (VALKYRIES pentapolar coding) and tagging (colours) in the UC.
 - CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims' information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: Use and evaluation of the TASSICA 3 triage card in the UC.

- **CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response:** Use of the Emergency Medical Services Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) as the standard for information exchange in UCs demonstrators.
- **CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response:** Deployment and evaluation of SIGRUN as an integration reference to facilitate the deployment and response of emergency services in the UC demonstrator.
- **CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response:** Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the UC.

The assessment of the enablers in the UC3 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:

- Questionnaires in the framework of the specific training actions of the UC3.
- Records made during the exercise: Collection (manually or automatically) of the information necessary to evaluate the MEs (mission success measures) and to determine whether or not the established KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) were met. These records were made
- On-line questionnaires at the end of the UC3 to collect the evaluation of the participants in the UC simulation.

A detailed description is included in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation - A1/Annex F”.

10.3. WP6 harmonization opportunities – BDI, please summarize with regard to the WP6 opportunities

The selected opportunities were implemented in UC3

- **CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data**
- **CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.**
- **CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions;**
- **CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).**

A detailed description is included in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation - A/1. Annex F”

10.3.1. CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

This opportunity has an identical implementation and validation in the 3 UCs, therefore, it is described in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation - A/1. Annex F”

10.3.2. CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.

This harmonization opportunity focuses on defining a minimum set of competences and skills required for volunteers involved in first aid operations in disaster scenarios. The objective is to harmonize the required competencies to ensure the proper integration of volunteers in field operational procedures.

The Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers was presented during the training day for UC3 before the real implementation of the exercise and was subject of evaluation by the participating first responders. The results are presented in Annex C

10.3.3. CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

The Joint Multinational Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) Course was developed to improve interoperability and joint civilian-military training and action during cross-border MCI. The course was presented and assessed during the UC3 training session. First, the course content, methodology, goals and tasks were presented to the cadets and military officers of the National Military University. The educational content of two of the most important lectures of the course was also presented to them. For the validation and testing of the course, the specially developed questionnaire, which includes eight open-ended and closed questions, was used. During the exercise, 17 people - military cadets and officers - were surveyed. Based on these results, some general conclusions were drawn (Annexes C and D).

10.3.4. CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).

This opportunity proposes the standardization of education and training for first aid responses (creation of a training kit: curriculum, training methodology and training manual). It defines the process of inspection of the Training kit containing curriculum, methodology, and training manual that have been developed to validate this opportunity at the European level.

11. Validation and testing – Analysis of the results

The results of the tests carried out for each opportunity are detailed below. Both the preliminary tests and the tests performed at the time of the exercise are described. The detailed description of each test performed is described in the verification and validation document D7.3 [3] and the methodology in D7.1 [3].

In this section, the summary of the results obtained is reported and the analysis of these data is performed.

Annex J. WP4 Results, Annex K. WP5 Results and Annex L. WP6 Results reflect the result sheets and describes in more detail the tests performed for each WP.

11.1. WP4 Results

11.1.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

11.1.1.1. Preliminary Tests

The preliminary tests were designed and performed prior to the Project demonstrators (UCs) to evaluate and verify that VALKYRIES solution provides the location data of the vehicles and supports their updating position while simultaneously distribute it to the different users that require such info, namely the GLOBAL_COP. The actual position of the victims and personnel can be provided by the mobile phones, as well as the vehicles equipped with a GPS/Galileo application.

The functions were tested firstly in test environment (remotely with simulating tools) and after in small drills performed at SUMMA112 facility. In these tests and drills the location functions were successfully tested.

Furthermore, initial validation tests were conducted for the UC1 (see D7.5), after which additional tests were made also for UC3.

Figure 11 - Example of the location of an ambulances during simulated remote tests in UC1

In the drills and test sessions performed, the location of the vehicles and its status was used to assign an ambulance to victims that were in need of transportation to a medical service / hospital.

Based on the lessons learned from UC1, further testing and validation of the opportunity was done in UC3. Below are presented some of the examples.

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Main Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History
TASS0022 []	June 14, 2023, 10:37 a.m. 3 months, 1 week ago	M	- / ADULT	Evacuated	MINOR	MINOR		AMBULANCE	St. Vrach HOSPITAL	→	→
TASS0031 []	June 14, 2023, 10:34 a.m. 3 months, 1 week ago	F	32 / ADULT	In destination	DELAYED	IMMEDIATE	TRAUMA ['abdomen/pelvis']	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vrach HOSPITAL	→	→
TASS0015 []	June 14, 2023, 10:35 a.m. 3 months, 1 week ago	M	- / ADULT	Evacuated	MINOR	MINOR		PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vrach HOSPITAL	→	→
TASS0035 []	June 14, 2023, 10:36 a.m.	M	56 /	Evacuated	MINOR	MINOR	TRAUMA ['lower	RMU -	St. Vrach	→	→

Figure 12 - Example of the location of an ambulances during simulated remote tests in UC3

The results of having the vehicles and victims' position and location were that it enabled a faster assignment and decision making by the incident manager, and hospitals are better prepared at time the victims arrived.

During the test all the features were validated, and any issues or limitation found were improved and corrected in the following sequence of tests and drills.

At the Bulgaria-Greece UC3, the tests were performed again where the location of the vehicles, assets and victims were made and tracked.

Figure 13 - UC3 Bulgaria - Greece Victims locations

As well as the vehicles' location was collected and mapped.

Figure 14 - UC3 Bulgaria – Greece Vehicles location

Combining both information, the MCI manager can decide the allocation of a vehicle to a victim. The position was updated regularly. Although with some delay, the data was updated within the limits established.

11.1.1.2. UC3 Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest Vehicles	The system MUST be able to generate an updated vehicles position picture that support the Operational Command to make better time dependent victims evacuation decisions	KPI 1: Information available	Yes (vehicles position was received at the GLOBAL_COP) => Success
		KPI 2: Updated position of vehicles	Updated vehicles Position at SIGRUN: average < half minute; => Success
		KPI 3: time elapses	Time to display the information of vehicle position: average < 1 minute. => Success

Table 7 – Results sheet CO.WP4-15-T01

Note: Globally the validation performed at this UC3 reinforced the previous results obtained in UC1 and tests. The response time obtained in UC3 were more time performing than the ones observed in in UC1.

11.1.2. CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace

11.1.2.1. Preliminary Tests

The preliminary testing of the system supporting Cross border functionality followed the same testing protocols used during the integration tests of the SIGRUN system. Such testing included:

- The correct use of the protocols for data exchanges
- Single entries
- No violation of the logical security of the SIGRUN system (unauthorized access to the systems or the data exchanged between all attached federated systems)
- Loads on the hardware of the IT systems used

Such checking was performed with special tools testing all logging encrypted data on a private Blockchain network following the Ethereum standards. Such tests were performed using third party tools such as

1. **Geth:** set up and test the Ethereum client
2. **Node.js, npm:** runtime environment and package manager
3. **Truffle Suite:** deploy and test smart contracts
4. **Web3.js:** interact with Ethereum nodes
5. **Git:** version control
6. **Remix:** deploy and debug smart contracts The private blockchain network was deployed using Raspberry Pis running all needed Ethereum protocols and algorithms on BC2050 servers.

11.1.2.2. UC3 Results

During UC3 execution, the performance of the systems monitoring the developed module for Blockchain logging of data, reported no errors or discrepancies as per the expected results of the tests before UC execution.

Transactions and data/metadata exchanged through SIGRUN were logged smoothly with no loss of information or duplicates, causing no significant load to the systems employed, as expected.

11.1.3. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges Results

11.1.3.1. Preliminary Tests

Several tests and verifications were performed prior to the UC3 and have been documented in Annex J. All of them were performed remotely. The day before the simulation, a general communications test was performed to verify 4G coverage and the exercise was executed on the site. The purpose of these tests was to verify that the pre-configured data was correct and that the integration with SIGRUN was working correctly. During the training sessions

To ensure the correct functioning of the tests, it is important that the applications have the corresponding URLs and APIs properly configured and that the master data of SIGRUN and the applications match. Most of the tests failed due to these configuration discrepancies or to communications issues.

This is the scenario configuration with Agencies involved mission and assets used for UC3 testing.

Departure/Arrival	Destination	Organization	Unit	Real Asset	Isafety Asset	Incident	Simulated Asset	
10:10	10:15	Collapsed Building	PDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 1 - FDFSCP-Sandanski	1 Fire Truck	BFSP FT01	Incident 1	Mission 1 - Scouting
10:10	10:15	Collapsed Building	RPD-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 1 - Local Police department -	1 Patrol	BP LPD01	Incident 1	Mission 2 - Control
10:25	10:35	Sport Center	PDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 5 - FDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	1 Vehicle	BFSP VHC01	Incident 1	Mission 3 - Control
10:35	10:40	Collapsed Building	PDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 4 - SOA- Blagoevgrad	1 Crew Transport	BFSP CRWT02	Incident 1	Mission 3 - Control
10:35	10:40	Collapsed Building	PDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 3 - SOA- Blagoevgrad	1 Crew Transport	BFSP CRWT01	Incident 1	Mission 3 - Control
11:00	11:05	Collapsed Building	Military Medical Academy	Medical Triage_Unit 2	1 Ambulance	BMA MTU02	Incident 1	Mission 4 - Medical Support
11:00	11:05	Collapsed Building	Hospital "St. Vrach" Sandanski	EMS	1 Ambulance	BEAS AMB01	Incident 1	Mission 4 - Medical Support
12:35	13:00	Struma River	PDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 2 - FDFSCP-Sandanski	1 Vehicle	BFSP FF01	Incident 3	Mission 1 - Scouting
12:35	13:00	Struma River	RPD-Blagoevgrad	UNIT 2 - Local Police department -	1 Patrol	BP LPD02	Incident 3	Mission 2 - Control
11:30	12:45	Struma River	Bulgarian Air Force	24 th Helicopter Air Base	1 Helicopter	BFSP HLC01	Incident 3	Mission 3 - Control
12:35	13:10	Struma River	Military Medical Academy	Medical Triage_Unit 1	1 Bus	BMA MTU01	Incident 3	Mission 4 - Control
11:05	11:10	Collapsed Building	Hellenic Rescue Team	USAR Department	1 Bus	HRT USAR	Incident 2	Mission 1 - Scouting
12:40	13:15	Struma River	Hospital "St. Vrach" Sandanski	EMS	1 Ambulance	BEAS AMB02	Incident 3	Mission 5 - Medical Support
12:40	13:15	Struma River	Municipality of Sandanski	Volunteer unit	1 Mini Bus	MoS VU	Incident 3	Mission 5 - Medical Support
12:40	13:15	Struma River	Hellenic Rescue Team	Water Rescue Department	1 Bus	HRT WRT	Incident 4	Mission 1 - Control
11:05	11:10	Collapsed Building	Hellenic NCA	ETIK	1 Vehicle	HNCA ETIK	Incident 2	Mission 2 - Control
11:05	11:10	Collapsed Building	Hellenic Fire Service	4th EMAK- Special Unit for Disasters	1 Crew Transport	HFS 4EMAK	Incident 2	Mission 2 - Control
11:05	11:10	Collapsed Building	Hellenic Fire Service	2th EMAK- Special Unit for Disasters	1 Crew Transport	HFS 2EMAK	Incident 2	Mission 2 - Control

Table 8 – Scenario configuration with Agencies involved mission and assets used for UC3 testing

11.1.3.2. UC3 Results

TEST	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-T03-Reduce Voice Communication	The test consists of verifying that the information update from SIGRUN is updated in real time in the Platform and the information is updated according to the central Database.	KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	420ms
		KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	595ms
		KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	655ms

Table 9 – Results from testing CO-WP4-42-T03

The general criteria for the KPI is as follows:

- < 60 sec | 100% successes;
- Between 60 and 90 sec | 50% successes;
- Between 90 to 120 sec | 25% success;
- > 120 sec | 0% success

The results show that the information is practically real time in a standard communications environment and therefore the results are very good. The digitisation of information and the use of command-and-control tools, triage and the SIGRUN reference model have a very high impact and decisions can be made more quickly at the command posts. In the traditional execution model, all information is transmitted by voice.

11.1.4. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

11.1.4.1. Preliminary Tests

The extraction of information from UC3 is characterised by the same way as the others, i.e., the extraction of data and the analysis of this data has been carried out in the same way. The differences in this use case are the amount of data that could be extracted and converted into the dataset. This data tells us how large and complex the simulation has been because, if there is a lot of real data, this means that many victims, vehicles and so on have been reproduced. The report of this specific use case is that we have a quantity of 2995 samples between simulated and real, obtaining not a great quantity as in UC1, but more than in the UC2. Detailed information on the analysis and description of the datasets can be found in D7.2.

11.1.4.2. UC3 Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-21-T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data from multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.	KPI 1: Adequacy: 90%	<i>Different data processing techniques have been applied to obtain the most important features, and then three Machine Learning models have been generated. The first one consists of predicting the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one. The second model predicts the patient's death after the first triage. The last model predicts the patient's worsening after the first triage. All information about the processing techniques and the generated models can be found in D.7.2.</i>
		KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: 5000 ms	

Table 10 – Results from testing CO-WP4-21-T01

11.2. WP5 Results

1.1.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Importance of all emergency services using a unified glossary to plan and respond to	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by respondents.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION			
MCI and disasters			
Verification action	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC3 previous tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Importance: 93,75% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 11 - Results sheet CO.WP5-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K – WP5 Result sheets

11.2.1. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

11.2.1.1. CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Stakeholder coding and labelling agreement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Cross-border cooperation improvement : The	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system.	5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	at least 80% by stakeholders.	
UC coding standardisation compliance: The degree of adherence in the UC to the standardised classification and coding of MCI victims proposed by VALKYRIES.	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 4: The information related to the triage of victims in SIGRUN complies with the standardised classification and coding proposed by VALKYRIES.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 96,88% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 87,50% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023.	
	Participants	Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece), Hellenic National Center for Emergency Assistance – EKAB (Greece), Hellenic Fire Service (Greece), Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (Sofia, Bulgaria), Sandanski Municipality Volunteers Unit (Bulgaria), Military Medical Academy (Bulgaria).	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 4: Coding compliance: YES (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION		
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 15 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC3 drill.
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 90,70% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 86,30% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 86% (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 12 - Results sheet CO.WP5-7-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance

See Annex K – WP5 Result sheets

11.2.2. CO.WP5-7-2 TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

self-reported score			
Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH /	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.	TOTALLY AGREED).		
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Stakeholder satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration (functional validation)
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged	Demonstration (functional validation)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 84,38% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 81,25% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 93,75% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 84,38% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Stakeholder satisfaction: 81,25% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 12 June 2023.	
	Participants	Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece), Hellenic National Center for Emergency Assistance – EKAB (Greece), Hellenic Fire Service (Greece), Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (Sofia, Bulgaria), Sandanski Municipality Volunteers Unit (Bulgaria), Military Medical Academy (Bulgaria).	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage threshold (TASSICA 3): 48,5 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: Triage accuracy rate (TASSICA 3): 91,18% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 13 - Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K – WP5 Result sheets

11.2.3. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 13 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 92% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 72% (NOT ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Online survey, 15 June 2023 and thereafter.	
	Participants	All participants in the UC3 drill.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 83,70% (ACHIEVED) • Predominant response: STRONGLY AGREE 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 14 - Results sheet CO.WP5-12-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K – WP5 Result sheets

11.2.4. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Implementation ease: The perceived ease and	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.	5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	at least 80% by stakeholders.	
First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
Satisfaction with the operating procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using SIGRUN.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration (functional validation)
Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using SIGRUN.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.	Demonstration (functional validation)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 13 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 88,00% (ACHIEVED) 	

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 80,00% (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 14 June 2023
	Participants	Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece), Hellenic National Center for Emergency Assistance – EKAB (Greece), Hellenic Fire Service (Greece), Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (Sofia, Bulgaria), Sandanski Municipality Volunteers Unit (Bulgaria), Military Medical Academy (Bulgaria).
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 10: Time to triage (SIGRUN): 121 sec (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 11: Triage accuracy (SIGRUN): 91,18% (ACHIEVED)
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 15 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC3 drill.
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 88,3% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 69,8% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 72,1% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 69,8% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 83,7% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 90,7% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 83,7% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 79% (NOT ACHIEVED)
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

	Result	Successful verification: YES
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Table 15 - Results sheet CO.WP5-13-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K – WP5 Result sheets

11.2.5. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
METHANE UC compliance: The degree of adherence of the incident information shared in the UC to the	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly shared METHANE data by the total	KPI 3: A result of at least 80% of compliance.	Demonstration (functional validation)

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
METHANE model.	METHANE dataset in the UC, expressed as a percentage).		
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 13 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 88,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 16 - Results sheet CO.WP5-3-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K – WP5 Result sheets

11.3. WP6 Results**11.3.1. CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data****11.3.1.1. Preliminary Tests**

Details on the methodology and design of the demonstrations carried out can be found in Deliverable D7.3.

11.3.1.2. UC Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	Verify that the data stored in the SIGRUN platform is correctly stored, applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it. Also, the data transmitted over the network is secure.	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success)	<i>The results obtained are that the information is 100% available and that the data is exchanged encrypted over the network thanks to https. On the other hand, for the simulations, the option of encrypting the data in the database has been highlighted to speed up its operation, but this option can be activated at any time.</i>
		KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications : encryption setting	
		KPI 3: data is stored with in an	

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
		encrypted format: encryption setting	

Table 17 - Results sheet CO.WP6-2-D01

11.3.2. CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.

11.3.2.1. Preliminary Tests

During the training phase of the UC3 (Unit of Coordination), a presentation session was conducted for the first responders on the use of the kit intended for volunteers. This kit represents an integral component of our development process.

11.3.2.2. UC3 Results

The training session was well-received by the initial responders. They actively participated and gave positive evaluations of the kit during the presentation phase (Please see Annex C for the feedback from the first responders).

11.3.3. CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

11.3.3.1. Preliminary Tests

During the UC3 preparation, a presentation session was held on the course content and methodology. The training set is designed for joint training of military and civilian specialists for joint actions during emergency situations.

11.3.3.2. UC3 Results

In general, the content, methodology and lecture materials proved were very well received by the training participants. The majority of test takers gave positive ratings to the kit during the performance phase (Please see Annex C for the feedback from the first responders).

11.3.4. CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

The implementation of this opportunity is related to the creation of a Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training kit for different groups of first responders who need to acquire basic knowledge and practical skills for performing life-saving activities in various types of trauma and medical conditions in case of cross-border MCI. This training kit contains curriculum, training methodology and training content/presentations. Focus is on train first responders in new technological solutions of VALKYRIES to enhance their abilities and capabilities to fight off the consequences of disasters.

11.3.4.1. Preliminary Tests

In the process of the development of the training kit, some preliminary tests were implemented of the presentations with paramedics in the Bulgarian Military Academy. The training of first responders how to use the VALKYRIES tools was done during the first UC3 planning workshop in December 2022 and the final planning conference in April 2023.

11.3.4.2. UC3 Results

During the UC3 execution, one whole day was devoted to presenting the VALKYRIES tools and the content of the Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training kit (Annex G Agenda for UC3 execution). After the training, the participating first responders filled out feedback questionnaire

and evaluated the training very positively (Please see Annex C for the feedback from the first responders).

11.4. Summary of stakeholders' feedback for the VALKYRIES solution and use case implementation

A total of 43 first responders from Bulgaria and Greece filled out the online feedback questionnaire about the VALKYRIES solutions (SIGRUN and digital applications) and presented training kit, as well as the overall satisfaction with the exercise. They come from Fire fighters, Medical first responders, volunteers and local authorities.

The Mean age of their experience in the field is 14 years, while the mode is 20 years.

Most of the first responders, ranging from 65 to 89 percent, strongly agree with the following statements:

- The SIGRUN solution is a highly valuable tool for their work.
- Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage Mass Casualty Incidents (MCIs).
- Using SIGRUN allows them to efficiently handle MCIs.
- The use of SIGRUN is beneficial for the accurate management of MCIs.
- Using SIGRUN simplifies the management of Multi-Casualty Incidents.
- The use of SIGRUN enhances the quality of Multi-Casualty Incidents management.

In addition, the majority of first responders participating in the survey expressed satisfaction with SIGRUN for serving and managing Multi-Casualty Incidents. They are also comfortable with my ability to use SIGRUN. Moreover, they find it easy to learn how to operate SIGRUN and believe that it can be seamlessly integrated with other technical systems currently in use by their organization for responding to MCIs.

Furthermore, according to the vast majority of first responders, the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution facilitates information sharing among different agencies involved in cross-border MCIs. They are highly likely to recommend that their first responder organization adopts and utilizes the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution.

The overall satisfaction of the first responders with the functionalities of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution is also high (86% give answers "Considerably" and "Greatly").

Biggest part of the first responders think that the demonstrated Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders will be helpful for the completion of their tasks in MCI (69.8% give answers "Considerably" and "Greatly"). The same is the share of the people that consider the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for as better compared to other existing training courses. Therefore, they would recommend to their or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the demonstrated Training Kit.

Finally, major part of the participants in the UC3 72.1% give answers "Considerably" and "Greatly" regarding their satisfaction with the content of the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders.

With respect to the demonstrated CIMIC Training Curriculum for first responders, the main part of the responders (62.8%) think that it enables the more successful implementation of their tasks in a cross-border Multi casualty Incidents. Close is the share of the participants in the UC3 (65.1%) that are satisfied with the content of the proposed CIMIC Training Curriculum.

High is also the level of satisfaction of the participants with the proposed Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content (72.1% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”).

The satisfaction of the participants from the preparation of the exercise (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics, etc.) is very high (83.7% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”).

Most of the participants are satisfied with the training that they received for the use of the proposed VALKYRIES technological solutions for the exercise (79.1% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”).

The predominant part of them (83.7% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”) when evaluate the scenario of the Use Case as realistic and responding to a potentially real life emergency.

High is also the evaluation of the overall coordination of the exercise (79.1% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”) and think that the coordination facilitated the effective collaboration between the participants.

The evaluation of the first responders is quite positive regarding the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support, etc.) of the exercise (86% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”).

Finally, the overall satisfaction with the conduct of the exercise is also very high (88.4% give answers “Considerably” and “Greatly”).

Detailed information of the feedback survey with UC3 first responders are presented in the Annex C.

12. Lessons learned

The planning and implementation of UC3 gave an opportunity to formulate some lessons learned. They are summarised in the following rows.

First, for the success of the exercise it is mandatory to establish well in advance strong cooperation among all contributing partners in the consortium, as well as the external experts, stakeholders, local authorities, etc. The planning for the UC3 started 8 months before its execution and the implementation plan was updated several times coordinated with the end users, local authorities and contributing partners of the VALKYRIES consortium.

Second, the UC3 execution demonstrated how important the joint multinational training of the participants is well in advance. Therefore, two trainings were organised how to use the VALKYRIES digital tools.

Third, the UC3 exercise confirmed the usefulness of the VALKYRIES project consortium proposals and verified the effectiveness of the digital triage application, as well as the TASSICA triage card.

Fourth, it is important always to organise feedback and debriefing session after the execution of the exercise and to give proper recognition of the contribution of the participants.

Fifth, the UC3 execution confirmed the importance of good cooperation with national and local media, as well as the proper use of social media. There were more than 10 publications presenting the exercise.

The exercise conducted demonstrated:

- Good coordination and cooperation achieved between different teams, agencies, and participants from the two countries - Bulgaria and Greece;
- The scenario was realistic and was well unfolded. The teams improvised when necessary and that was considered a positive asset as real situations require the preparedness and flexibility to perform out of the boundaries.
- The information that is entered in the SIGRUN platform and visualized through the Global COP allows it to be used as a database by all, to search for information by victim number, by types of trauma, and others. Critically important information is provided.
- Sharing information through the Global COP system and SIGRUN platform requires some preparation in advance. However, it has been proved and admitted that the use of the platform facilitates and accelerates information sharing and it allows geospatial visualization of resources deployed, thus providing fast Common Operational picture. Data storage and traceability is ensured and first responders expressed their satisfaction that all data was safely transferred, cross-checked and saved.
- The use of the VALKYRIES tools allowed the fast exchange of information in direct and accurate manner, reducing the need for multiple oral exchanges and the respective potential erroneous communication among the responders in the field and the staff in the command posts. This way, sources of errors are reduced as well as the necessary time to be spent in audio communication and necessary corrections, allowing the responders to focus in their operational activities.
- The end-users, during the After-Action review meeting, shared their opinion on different technical details and content of all VALKYRIES tools employed and expressed their satisfaction on their ease-of-use, while confirming that training is required.
- Common operational picture and situational awareness is shared between all actors involved in a standardized manner, and this is of particular importance for cross-border

operations where multiple parties, languages and standard operating procedures are involved.

- Conceptually, strengthening the digital dimension in emergency response has evident benefits in both command and control and field operations. However, considering that all technological tools rely heavily on electricity and communications network, it was being shared that availability and knowledge of traditional means should not be disregarded.
- The objectives of the UC3 Bulgaria-Greece demonstrations are achieved. Technical and human interoperability is a prerequisite for a successful operation in disaster response and both have been achieved by the full-scale exercise of UC3.

Recommendations:

- Critically important information is provided, but first aid responders believe that triage is not that important. Rather, finding and removing victims from the site of the disaster is more important. One can think about improving the applications.
- If there are multiple victims e.g., more than a hundred, there will probably be a problem in the Field Operational Centre. It could be considered to improve the Global COP application to have a clear picture when the victims are several hundred people.
- The end-users both those acting in the field and in the command posts shared some insights as far as the technological functionalities of VALKYRIES solutions are concerned, e.g., important recommendation is to have more clear boundaries between the extraction phase of the rescuers (first triage) and the second triage conducted by the paramedics, otherwise the location and status of the victims during this intermediate phase is not clear.
- Further testing of the solutions in more difficult operating conditions, especially the triage tool in the field, would be needed prior to the commercialization of the tool, so as to ensure its usability in multiple environments and/or recommend additional functionalities.
- Integration of all tools in a common platform at operational basis, supported by the relevant regulatory framework, will allow a secure and accurate transfer of data for successful multi-stakeholder operations.

13. Conclusions (Summary of the debriefing, recommendations and lessons learned)

The UC3 was deemed a success by the first responders. More than 140 participants from various national institutions, including the fire brigade, EMS, police, local authorities, and volunteers, contributed to the success of the exercise and the testing of the VALKYRIES solutions. The two-day exercise provided an opportunity to compare the traditional way of executing tasks with the application of the VALKYRIES solution. The success of the exercise was attributed to the establishment of strong cross-border and cross-sectorial collaboration. Over 40 First Responders participated in the feedback survey and gave highly positive evaluations. The UC3 execution gained significant visibility in national, local, and social media. As important evidence of the achieved goals, here are some statements from the first responders during the lessons learned session:

- "The scenario was well-developed, realistic, and helped make the training come to life."
- "The information entered into the SIGRUN platform and visualized through the Global COP can be used as a database by everyone to search for information by victim number, type of trauma, and more. It provides critically important information."
- "Sharing information through the Global COP system and SIGRUN platform requires good advance preparation, but using the apps makes everything easier and faster. Considering the overall picture, the benefits are evident, and everyone did an excellent job."
- "During the exercise using the traditional approach, firefighters received numerous calls and had conversations, leading to errors in the first triage. However, by using the VALKYRIES digital app on their smartphones on the second day, they significantly reduced the number of calls and focused on triage, which greatly reduced the errors they made."
- "Using the VALKYRIES tools during training demonstrated their usefulness and ease of use. There is no doubt that all tests were successful and generally positive."
- "Conceptually, by incorporating a digital dimension, we enhance command and control, allowing for faster and more efficient traditional methods."
- "The objectives of the UC3 Bulgaria-Greece demonstrations have been successfully achieved."

14. References and bibliography

1. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D4.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"
2. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D2.8 Architecture Design Document"
3. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation"
4. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.4 Reference Integration and Lesson Learned Report"
5. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.1 Test Bed and Evaluation Methodology"

15. Annex A - Glossary

Acronym	Description
112	EU emergency phone number
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
C2	Command-and-Control
CIMIC	Civil-Military Cooperation
EMS	Emergency Medical Service
EUCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
EX	Exercise
EXSPEC	EXSPEC – Exercise Specification (also Demonstration Specification)
FBD	Fire brigade Department
FOC	Field Operational Centre
FR	First Responder
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service (firefighters)
FTS	Field Triage Station
FX	Field Exercise
GD FSPP Mol	General Directorate "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of Mol
GP	GLOBAL COP (one of the tools)
GSCP	General Secretary of Civil Protection in Greece
HRT	The Hellenic Rescue Team
iSC2	iSafety C2 (one of the tools)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIVEX	Live Exercise (also FX - Field Exercise)
OHQ	Operational Head Quarters
PD	Police Department
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
SAR	Search and Rescue
SOP	Standard Operative Procedures
UC	Use Case
VF	Voluntary Formations

Table 18 - Glossary

16. Annex B – Detailed implementation plan

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

for execution of the main activities and participating actors in the Cross-border Bulgarian – Greece Exercise (UC3) for the traditional exercise on 12.06.2023 and VALKYRIES solution on 14.06.2023

Place: The outskirts of the city of Sandanski (coordinates N 41°33.0864 / E 23°16.3144 /).
41.55273633570222, 23.272661283755166 ul. "Svoboda" 51, 2800 Sandanski
<https://goo.gl/maps/31qYB4y6URdaRwvn9?coh=178571&entry=tt>

Participants:

- Bulgarian Defence Institute (BDI) – Exercise director;
- KEMEA – Exercise co-director - 4;
- HRT -6 people;
- AREU – 3 people;
- Regional Directorate Fire Safety and Protection of Population (FSPP) for execution the role of the Operational Headquarters of the Regional Directorate Blagoevgrad;
- Regional Police Department of the town of Sandanski;
- The Mayor of city of Sandanski and members of the Operational Headquarters
- National Centre of Emergency Call "112" (simulated);
- Field Operating Centre, Sandanski;
- Voluntary formation from Sandanski municipality – 10 people;
- Bulgarian Air Force, the military formation 32040 – Krumovo; - 1 helicopter
- Specialized disaster medicine team from the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy; 4 people and an ambulance;
- First aid unit and an ambulance from Sandanski municipality;
- National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography, Bulgarian Academy of Science (Simulated role);
- Political Liaison (Simulated role);
- Citizens (Real actors/cadets);
- Foreign country citizens in need of evacuation (Real actors/cadets);
- Victims (Real actors/cadets);
- Hellenic EMS Team – 6 people;
- Hellenic police – 1 person;
- Hellenic Fire Service – 7 people;

Nº	Operating time	Event	Expected actions	Participating forces	Defendant
1.	05:43	10:00 – 10:05	Earthquake incident happened in South-Western Bulgaria between the towns of Sandanski and Petrich with epicentre at 16 kilometres from the border with a magnitude of 6.9 on the Richter scale.	From the National institute of geophysics, geodesy and geography of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences sends data for the earthquake to the National Operating Centre of the General Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection. From there the information is passed to Regional Operating Centre of the fire department, located in the fire department in city of Blagoevgrad.	- Duty officers at the Regional Operating Centre
2.	05:48	10:05 – 10:15	The National Centre of Emergency Call "112" received numerous reports of destruction in the area and many injured people /simulated by the Regional Operating Centre of the fire department/	The National Centre of Emergency Call "112" operator on duty informs National Operating Centre and Regional Operating Centre of the fire department, police call centre and emergency centre. The Regional Operating Centre informs the fire department in Sandanski, local police department and emergency teams. Following the procedures, fire trucks in the fire departments in Sandanski are taken outside the garages. Teams from fire department are dispatched to the accidents.	- National Operating Centre of the FD - Regional Operating Centre of the FD - Police call centre - National Centre of Emergency Call "112"/simulated/
3.	05:55 ÷06.10	10:05 – until the end	Police Call Centre announces and includes forces.	Take action according to operational procedures, collect information and report according to the established order.	- Police Department of Sandanski
4.	06:10÷06.15	10:25 - 10:30	Arrival of the first forces at the scene of the accident /residential building on the outskirts in city of Sandanski with coordinates N 41 ^o 33.0864 / E 23 ^o 16.3144 /	The first on-site supervisor relays information to Regional Operating Centre and reports to many injured, fire in the building as a result of the earthquake and much destruction to the building. He asks for additional rescue and search teams.	- One team from Fire Department (FD) of Sandanski
5.	06:15÷06.20	10:30 – 10:35	The Regional Operating Centre received information from On-site manager about the damage of the earthquake	Duty officer at regional operating centre informs the Director of the Regional Fire Department about the situation and reports to the National Operating Centre for the taken actions	- National Operating Centre of the FD - Regional Operating Centre of the FD - duty officers in local FD in Sandanski
6.	06:20÷06.25	10:45 – 10:50	The National Operating Centre of the FD received information from Ministry of Environment and	National Operating Centre of the FD informs the National Centre of Emergency Call "112" for the new information	- National Operating Centre of the FD

Nº	Operating time	Event	Expected actions	Participating forces	Defendant
			Water about the sudden drop in the level of the Logodaj dam near city of Blagoevgrad.		- Regional Operating Centre of the FD - Duty officers in local FD in Sandanski
7.	06.35÷06.40	11:00 - 11:05	The Director of Regional Fire Department implements the Crisis, Emergency And Disaster Response Plan in the earthquake and floods section	<p>1. The Regional Operating Centre notifies all personnel of the Fire Department in Sandanski, Specialized Operational Activities Team and the Operational Headquarters of the Directorate.</p> <p>2. The Regional Operating Centre orders additional forces and resources to go to the accidents.</p> <p>3. The Regional Operating Centre reports to the National Operating Centre for the taken actions.</p>	- One more fire truck from FD Sandanski with 6 firefighters - One Specialized Operational Activities Team with 5 members and 1 vehicle
8.	06:40÷06.45	11:05 – 11:10	The Mayor of Sandanski received information for the situation from the Director of the regional fire department /simulated/	The Mayor of Sandanski gave an order to gather the members of the Regional Headquarters and to activate the Disaster Recovery Plan in the earthquake section. Chief of Staff is the Mayor of Sandanski. For operational management is selected the representative of the fire department. /simulated by the local authorities/ Operational Headquarters of the Regional Directorate is dispatched on site. (Sandanski Sports Centre)	- The Mayor of Sandanski and the other members of the Regional Headquarter, who also be represented by members of the local Municipality
9.	06.50÷ 09.15	11:15 – until the end of the UC3 execution	The Operational Headquarters of the Regional Directorate is dispatched on site, takes over the leadership and, if necessary, attracts representatives of the other first responder units to its composition	The Bulgarian Operational Headquarters OHQ assesses the situation and deployed to provide additional forces and funds from emergency teams, PD, Voluntary Formations (VF) from Sandanski, military formations (simulated by cadets) for construction of triage points, extraction and transport of the injured to a hospital. The OHQ provides a corridor for the movement of fire and rescue equipment to the scene of the accident and back, cordoning off the area and ensuring a permeable regime in the area of the accident site and the safety of the headquarters, keeps a record of the number and nationality of the victims.	- Members of the Operational Headquarters of the Regional Directorate

Nº	Operating time	Event	Expected actions	Participating forces	Defendant
				<p>The OHQ requires a helicopter crew from the military formation 32040 - Krumovo, to carry out reconnaissance and assess the situation in the area.</p> <p>The OHQ requires from Ministry of Health construction of the Field centres for reception, sorting by type and degree of disabilities (medical triage) by a doctor specializing in emergency medicine, treatment and preparation of the injured for transport and evacuation from the area.</p> <p>The Field centres support the implementation of first psychological support and primary collection of information about the victims</p>	
10.	09:15	11:15	The Mayor of Sandanski district receives from the Director of the Regional FD the request for a helicopter from the Operational Headquarters	The Mayor of Sandanski sends a request to the Ministry of Defense / Chief of Defense for the use of aircraft from the military formation 32040 - Krumovo to conduct a reconnaissance operation	- The the Mayor of Sandanski
11.	09:30	11:30 – 11:45/ timeline depends on the time of the flight /	At the Air Base “Krumovo”, a helicopter is being prepared for take-off and participation in the area reconnaissance operation	Flight control officer received information for the planned helicopter flight from the Air Base “Krumovo” from military formation 32040, to the reconnaissance area and requests that flight information will be transmitted to him (flight plan, estimated and actual time on the routes to the zone).	- The military formation 32040 - Krumovo
12.	09:45÷10.30	11:45 – until the end	Restricting flights over the accident area.	The crew of the helicopter from the military formation 32040 - Krumovo conducts a search for victims using specialized equipment for searching and locating people through a broadcast signal from mobile cellular receivers and thermal cameras.	- A helicopter from the Military formation 32040 – Krumovo will participate in the operation.
13.	10:30÷10.45	12:30 – 12:45 AM	The helicopter crew discovers the location of the flooded and threatened areas by external signs.	The crew of the military air force helicopter transmits information about the scale of the accident, continues the inspection of the area and provides information about the situation, suitable roads, approaches, etc.	- A helicopter from the Military formation 32040 – Krumovo.
14.	10:45	11:15 – 11:30	A request has been received between the two border municipalities on both sides of the border for the inclusion in the rescue operations of first aid teams from	Teams from the Hellenic Republic arrive by bilateral Bulgaria – Greece agreement or standard operating procedures (simulated). First aid teams from Greece come to the OHQ, who is located in city of Sandanski and from there they are send to report	- First aid teams from Greece arrive - OHQs of the Hellenic municipality (simulated)

Nº	Operating time	Event	Expected actions	Participating forces	Defendant
			the Republic of Greece.	to the Field Operations Centre for inclusion in the rescue operations. Operational Headquarters of the Hellenic Municipality is deployed near the Bulgarian-Greece border (simulated). Operational information about the actions taken and a shared Common Operational Picture (COP) of the situation is shared via the SIGRUN platform to the two OHQs on both sides of the border (simulated).	- Bulgarian OHQ and Greece OHQs (simulated)
15.	10:45÷ 12.15	10:30 - until the end	Search and rescue operations for victims of the earthquake and extinguishing local outbreaks	<u>First Operational Section - Extraction of victims from a collapsed residential building</u> 1. Fire-fighting actions in one with strengthening the building, which goes into rescue and extraction of the injured in the building. 2. Construction of a Field centre for rescue, first medical aid and psychological support of the injured. - Distribution of the injured (triage), first medical aid, preparation for transportation to medical facilities. Setting up a casualty triage stations (Building and Struma River). - A Field Triage Station was established with adequate safety measures. - Information and a Common Operational Picture are shared through the SIGRUN platform between the OHQs of Bulgaria and Greece (simulated).	- One fire truck from FD Sandanski - Specialized operational activities from Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection - Specialized disaster medicine team from the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy - Ambulance team from Sandanski hospital (EMS) - Police Department Team - Rescue team from Greece - Bulgarian and Greece OHQs.
16.	12.15÷13.00	12:15 - until the end of UC3 execution	Search and rescue operations for foreign country citizens affected by the earthquake and in need of evacuation	<u>Second Operational Section - Extraction the victims from collapsed hostel</u> where foreign country citizens are accommodated. The firefighters and rescue team provide an Initial triage of the victims and first aid is given. Those who need an evacuation and hospitalization are transported by ambulance.	- Specialized operational activities from Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection - Rescue team from Greece - Minibus from Sandanski municipality
17.	13:00÷ 14.00	13:00 - until the end of UC3	Rescuing victims of the flood, limiting the spill of hazardous	<u>Third Operational Section - Extraction of victims from the Struma river, limitation of flooded areas and stop the spill of hazardous chemicals</u>	- One fire truck from FD Sandanski - Specialized operational

Nº	Operating time	Event	Expected actions	Participating forces	Defendant
		execution app. 18.30	materials and building dikes /spot on the river Struma nearby city of Sandanski with coordinates N 41°30.3398 / E 23°15.1289 /	<p>1. Construction of dikes in the flooded areas to prevent the scale of the flood.</p> <p>2. Limiting the spill of hazardous substances/ the reason is chemical leak in the river from threatment of the nearby agriculture fields/ in the Struma River.</p> <p>3. Rescuing and evacuating people and movable property from flooded areas.</p> <p>4. Construction of a Field centre for rescue, first medical aid and psychological support of the injured.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution of the injured (triage), first medical aid for the wounded and probably affected people from the agricultural chemicals, preparation for transportation to medical facilities. Setting up a casualty triage station.; - A Field Triage Station is established with adequate safety measures. <p>5. The OHQ checks the possibility of attracting unmanned aerial vehicles (drones) for reconnaissance and coordination of forces by means of video broadcasting in the area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is required to mobilize the drones available in FD. - Information and a Common Operational Picture are shared through the SIGRUN platform between the OHQs of Bulgaria and Greece (simulated). 	<p>activities from Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specialized Disaster Medicine Team from the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy - Ambulance team from Sandanski hospital (EMS) - Police Department team - Voluntary formation from Sandanski municipality /rescue teams from Greece/ - Bulgarian and Greece OHQs (simulated).
18.	After completing rescue activities for all survivors	After completing rescue activities for all survivors	End of exercise	The on-site managers decide to end search and rescue operations and informs the Bulgarian OHQs and Greek OHQs (simulated)	- All participants
19.	10.00÷13.30	10.00÷13.30	After action review on 15 th June 2023 at the conference room	<p>The on-site manager carries out a brief analysis of the activities implemented, evaluates the objectives that are achieved and gives some instructions for the next actions upon completion of the exercise.</p> <p>All first responders participating in the exercise fill out evaluation questionnaire.</p>	- All participants

Table 19 – Detailed implementation plan

17. Annex C – Results from feedback survey first responders.

Frequency Tables

1.1. Type of first responder's organization?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Civil protection	1	2.3	2.3	2.3
	Fire fighters	10	23.3	23.3	25.6
	Medical first responders	12	27.9	27.9	53.5
	Other	14	32.6	32.6	86.0
	Volunteers	6	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

1.2. Years of experience as a first responder

Mean	13.07
Median	11.00
Mode	20

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	2.3	2.3	2.3
	2	3	7.0	7.0	9.3
	3	1	2.3	2.3	11.6
	4	2	4.7	4.7	16.3
	5	3	7.0	7.0	23.3
	6	3	7.0	7.0	30.2
	7	1	2.3	2.3	32.6
	9	3	7.0	7.0	39.5
	10	3	7.0	7.0	46.5
	11	2	4.7	4.7	51.2

1.2. Years of experience as a first responder

Mean	13.07
Median	11.00
Mode	20

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
12	2	4.7	4.7	55.8
13	2	4.7	4.7	60.5
15	2	4.7	4.7	65.1
16	2	4.7	4.7	69.8
18	1	2.3	2.3	72.1
20	5	11.6	11.6	83.7
23	1	2.3	2.3	86.0
25	1	2.3	2.3	88.4
26	2	4.7	4.7	93.0
30	2	4.7	4.7	97.7
35	1	2.3	2.3	100.0
Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.1. I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for my work.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	19	44.2	44.2	44.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	8	18.6	18.6	62.8
	Strongly agree	16	37.2	37.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.2. I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for our organization.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	22	51.2	51.2	51.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	8	18.6	18.6	69.8
	Strongly agree	13	30.2	30.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.3. Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage Multi casualty incidents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	20	46.5	46.5	46.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	7	16.3	16.3	62.8
	Strongly agree	16	37.2	37.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.4. Using SIGRUN allows me to quickly manage Multi casualty incidents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	23	53.5	53.5	53.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	4	9.3	9.3	62.8
	Strongly agree	16	37.2	37.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.5. The use of SIGRUN is useful to correctly manage the Multi casualty incidents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	20	46.5	46.5	46.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	8	18.6	18.6	65.1
	Strongly agree	15	34.9	34.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.6. I am satisfied with SIGRUN to serve and manage the Multi casualty incident

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	9	20.9	20.9	60.5
	Strongly agree	17	39.5	39.5	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.7. Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage Multi casualty incidents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	21	48.8	48.8	48.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	8	18.6	18.6	67.4
	Strongly agree	14	32.6	32.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.8. The use of SIGRUN increases the quality of Multi casualty incidents management.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	10	23.3	23.3	62.8
	Strongly agree	16	37.2	37.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.9. I can manage the Multi casualty incidents correctly every time I use SIGRUN.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	15	34.9	34.9	34.9
	Disagree	1	2.3	2.3	37.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	12	27.9	27.9	65.1
	Strongly agree	15	34.9	34.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.10. I feel comfortable with my SIGRUN ability.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Disagree	1	2.3	2.3	39.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	10	23.3	23.3	62.8
	Strongly agree	16	37.2	37.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.11. Learning to operate SIGRUN is easy for me.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	19	44.2	44.2	44.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	9	20.9	20.9	65.1
	Strongly agree	15	34.9	34.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.12. It is easy for me to be proficient in using SIGRUN.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	24	55.8	55.8	55.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	7	16.3	16.3	72.1
	Strongly agree	12	27.9	27.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.13. SIGRUN gives error messages that clearly tell me how to troubleshoot.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Disagree	2	4.7	4.7	44.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	18	41.9	41.9	86.0
	Strongly agree	5	11.6	11.6	97.7
	Strongly disagree	1	2.3	2.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.14. Every time I make a mistake using SIGRUN, I recover easily and quickly.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	18	41.9	41.9	41.9
	Disagree	3	7.0	7.0	48.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	13	30.2	30.2	79.1
	Strongly agree	9	20.9	20.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.15. The information (such as online help, on-screen messages and other documentation) provided with the SIGRUN is clear.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	21	48.8	48.8	48.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	32.6	32.6	81.4
	Strongly agree	8	18.6	18.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.16. The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	21	48.8	48.8	48.8
	Disagree	3	7.0	7.0	55.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	10	23.3	23.3	79.1
	Strongly agree	9	20.9	20.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

2.17. The operation of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution requires significant technical competence by the first responder to effectively use it.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Disagree	9	20.9	20.9	58.1
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	32.6	32.6	90.7
	Strongly agree	3	7.0	7.0	97.7
	Strongly disagree	1	2.3	2.3	100.0
	Total		43	100.0	100.0

2.18. The proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution can easily be integrated with other currently used technical systems and followed by your organization for the response to an Multi casualty incident.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	18	41.9	41.9	41.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	13	30.2	30.2	72.1
	Strongly agree	12	27.9	27.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

3. To what extent the proposed VALKYRIES project SGRUN solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerable	21	48.8	48.8	48.8
	Great	17	39.5	39.5	88.4
	Moderate	5	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

4. To what extent did you experience difficulties when using the proposed VALKYRIES project SGRUN solution?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerable	12	27.9	27.9	27.9
	Great	6	14.0	14.0	41.9
	Limited	9	20.9	20.9	62.8
	Moderate	12	27.9	27.9	90.7
	Not at all	4	9.3	9.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

5. How likely is you to suggest to yours first responder organization to adopt and use the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely likely	14	32.6	32.6	32.6
	Likely	19	44.2	44.2	76.7
	Neutral	10	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

6. Does the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution bring added value to the management of and response to cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	25	58.1	58.1	58.1
	Greatly	14	32.6	32.6	90.7
	Moderately	4	9.3	9.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

7. Overall, are you satisfied with the functionalities of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	23	53.5	53.5	53.5
	Greatly	14	32.6	32.6	86.0
	Moderately	6	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

8. To what extent the training with the presented Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders will be helpful for the completion of your tasks in Multi casualty Incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	15	34.9	34.9	34.9
	Greatly	15	34.9	34.9	69.8
	I don't know/I have no experience	2	4.7	4.7	74.4
	Moderate	11	25.6	25.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

9. To what extent the training with the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border Multi casualty Incidents (MCI) compared to the existing training courses?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	19	44.2	44.2	44.2
	Greatly	11	25.6	25.6	69.8
	I don't know/I have no experience	3	7.0	7.0	76.7
	Moderate	10	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

10. How likely is to recommend to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders in Multi casualty Incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Greatly	14	32.6	32.6	69.8
	I don't know/I have no experience	3	7.0	7.0	76.7
	Limited	2	4.7	4.7	81.4
	Moderate	8	18.6	18.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

11. Overall, are you satisfied with the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Greatly	14	32.6	32.6	72.1
	I don't know/I have no experience	3	7.0	7.0	79.1
	Moderate	9	20.9	20.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

12. To what extent the training with the proposed CIMIC Training Curriculum for first responders enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border Multi casualty Incidents (MCI) compared to the existing training courses?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Greatly	11	25.6	25.6	62.8
	I don't know/I have no experience	6	14.0	14.0	76.7
	Moderate	10	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

13. Overall, to what extent you are satisfied with the proposed CIMIC Training Curriculum for first responders in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	15	34.9	34.9	34.9
	Greatly	13	30.2	30.2	65.1
	I don't know/I have no experience	6	14.0	14.0	79.1
	Moderate	9	20.9	20.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

14. Overall, to what extent you are satisfied with the proposed Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerably	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Greatly	15	34.9	34.9	72.1
	I don't know/I have no experience	5	11.6	11.6	83.7
	Moderate	7	16.3	16.3	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

15. To what extent you agree or disagree that it is important that all emergency medical services use the same classification to designate the triage priority of victims in Multi casualty incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	13	30.2	30.2	30.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	4	9.3	9.3	39.5
	Strongly agree	26	60.5	60.5	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

16. To what extent you agree or disagree with the naming of the triage priorities used in the trial conducted?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	6	14.0	14.0	51.2
	Strongly agree	21	48.8	48.8	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

17. To what extent you agree or disagree with the allocation of colours for the different priorities used in the test?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	5	11.6	11.6	48.8
	Strongly agree	22	51.2	51.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

18. To what extent you agree or disagree that the use of the same classification and colour coding throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	8	18.6	18.6	18.6
	Neither agree nor disagree	6	14.0	14.0	32.6
	Strongly agree	29	67.4	67.4	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

19. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the data transmitted in the exercise are appropriate for the proper management of victims by an emergency medical service in Multi casualty incidents?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	7	16.3	16.3	55.8
	Strongly agree	19	44.2	44.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

20. Do you think that the information conveyed in the initial incident statement test is appropriate for the needs of an emergency service in the first moments of an MCI or disaster?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	18	41.9	41.9	41.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	9	20.9	20.9	62.8
	Strongly agree	16	37.2	37.2	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

21. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the proposed VALKYRIES project solution SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between the different health services involved in the response to a Multi casualty incident?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	7	16.3	16.3	53.5
	Strongly agree	20	46.5	46.5	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

22. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the tested operative procedure would allow you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	2.3	2.3	2.3
Agree	16	37.2	37.2	39.5
Neither agree nor disagree	12	27.9	27.9	67.4
Strongly agree	14	32.6	32.6	100.0
Total	43	100.0	100.0	

23. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the tested procedure would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to a Multi casualty incident?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	16	37.2	37.2	37.2
Neither agree nor disagree	12	27.9	27.9	65.1
Strongly agree	15	34.9	34.9	100.0
Total	43	100.0	100.0	

24. Please rate your satisfaction as far as the preparation of the exercise is concerned (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics).

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Considerable	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
Great	19	44.2	44.2	83.7
Moderate	7	16.3	16.3	100.0
Total	43	100.0	100.0	

25. Please rate your satisfaction on the training you received for the use of the proposed VALKYRIES technological solutions for the exercise.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerable	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Great	17	39.5	39.5	79.1
	Little	1	2.3	2.3	81.4
	Moderate	8	18.6	18.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

26. To what extent was the scenario of the Use Case realistic and responding to a potentially real life emergency?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerable	23	53.5	53.5	53.5
	Great	13	30.2	30.2	83.7
	Little	1	2.3	2.3	86.0
	Moderate	6	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

27. How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerable	17	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Great	17	39.5	39.5	79.1
	Moderate	9	20.9	20.9	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

28. How would you rate the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support) of the exercise?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Excellent	19	44.2	44.2	44.2
	Good	18	41.9	41.9	86.0
	Moderate	6	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

29. Overall, to what extent were you satisfied with the conduct of the exercise?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Considerable	20	46.5	46.5	46.5
	Great	18	41.9	41.9	88.4
	Moderate	5	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	43	100.0	100.0	

18. Annex D – Feedback questionnaire for first responders

QUESTIONNAIRE

FOR FEED-BACK SURVEY WITH FIRST RESPONDERS PARTICIPATING IN THE JOINT BULGARIAN – GREEK CROSS-BORDER EXERCISE IN RESPONSE TO MULTI CASUALTY INCIDENTS

Dear Colleague,

Yesterday you participated in the joint Bulgarian – Greek exercise carried out in the framework of the European project VALKYRIES which aims to develop, implement and validate innovative technological solutions, operative procedures, education, training (E&T) and collaboration approaches in cross-sector, cross-border Multi casualty incidents (MCI). These are events where the number of victims far exceeds local resources and capabilities, which overwhelm the local healthcare system, at least for a period of time.

The role of this questionnaire is to receive feed-back evaluation from you of the demonstrated technological tools, operative procedures and E&T materials to improve collaboration among the first responders from different nations and different institutions.

We would like to ask you particularly to evaluate the VALKYRIES integrated solution named SIGRUN. This is a platform which integrates data from different sources and supports the Command and Control System (C2) in case of Multi casualty incidents (INDRA iSAFTY Application Modules for C2), visualizes the integrated data and creates a Common Operational Picture on both sides of the border (PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP) and provides digitalization of the triage, as well as traceability of the patients (Application for Digitalizing Triage Process and ARATOS and BlockChain2050 bracelet Tap2SOS).

We strongly rely on your expert opinion to boost up the pre-standardization of the VALKYRIES project solutions at the EU level.

Thank you for your cooperation!

VALKYRIES Joint Bulgarian – Greek exercise Team

General Information

Type of first responder's organization:

Role in organization:

Years of experience:

1. Please select which of the VALKYRIES solutions you have been using during the joint Bulgarian – Greek exercise (multiple answers are possible).

	Yes	No
▪ INDRA: iSAFTY Application Modules for C2	1	2
▪ PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP)	1	2
▪ Application for Digitalizing Triage Process	1	2
▪ ARATOS and BlockChain2050 bracelet Tap2SOS	1	2

2. We are suggesting you a series of statements. Please express your opinion for each of them choosing one of the answers on the scale.

2.1. I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for my work.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.2. I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for our organization.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.3. Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage Multi casualty incidents.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.4. Using SIGRUN allows me to quickly manage Multi casualty incidents.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.5. The use of SIGRUN is useful to correctly manage the Multi casualty incidents.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.6. I am satisfied with SIGRUN to serve and manage the Multi casualty incidents.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.7. Using SIGRUN makes it easier **to manage** Multi casualty incidents.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.8. The use of SIGRUN increases the **quality** of Multi casualty incidents management.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.9. I can manage the Multi casualty incidents correctly every time I use SIGRUN.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.10. I feel comfortable with my SIGRUN ability.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.11. Learning to operate SIGRUN is easy for me.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.12. It is easy for me to be proficient in using SIGRUN.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.13. SIGRUN gives error messages that clearly tell me how to troubleshoot.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.14. Every time I make a mistake using SIGRUN, I recover easily and quickly.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.15. The information (such as online help, on-screen messages and other documentation) provided with the SIGRUN is clear.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.16. The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.17. The operation of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution requires significant technical competence by the first responder to effectively use it.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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2.18. The proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution can easily be integrated with other currently used technical systems and followed by your organization for the response to an Multi casualty incident.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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3. To what extent the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1
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4. To what extent did you experience difficulties when using the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution?

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1
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5. How likely is you to suggest to yours first responder organization to adopt and use the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution?

Extremely likely 5	Likely 4	Neutral 3	Unlikely 2	Extremely unlikely 1
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6. Does the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution bring added value to the management of and response to cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderately 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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7. Overall, are you satisfied with the functionalities of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderately 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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8. To what extent the training with the presented Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders will be helpful for the completion of your tasks in Multi casualty Incidents?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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9. To what extent the training with the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border Multi casualty Incidents (MCI) compared to the existing training courses?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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10. How likely is to recommend to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders in Multi casualty Incidents?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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11. Overall, are you satisfied with the proposed Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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12. To what extent the training with the proposed CIMIC Training Curriculum for first responders enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border Multi casualty Incidents (MCI) compared to the existing training courses?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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13. Overall, to what extent you are satisfied with the proposed CIMIC Training Curriculum for first responders in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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14. Overall, to what extent you are satisfied with the proposed Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers in Multi casualty Incidents in terms of content?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	I don't know/I have no experience 99
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TIS PART OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE CONCERNS THE FIRST RESPONDERS THAT WERE RESPONSIBLE FOR THE TRIAGE DURING THE EXERCISE. IF YOU WERE NOT INVOLVED IN THE TRIAGE, PLEASE GO TO THE QUESTION 25 EVALUATION OF THE EXERCISE

UNIFICATION OF TRIAGE PRIORITY CODING AND TAGGING IN MCI (E.WP5-3)

- 15. To what extent you agree or disagree that it is important that all emergency medical services use the same classification to designate the triage priority of victims in Multi casualty incidents?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 16. To what extent you agree or disagree with the naming of the triage priorities used in the trial conducted?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 17. To what extent you agree or disagree with the allocation of colours for the different priorities used in the test?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 18. To what extent you agree or disagree that the use of the same classification and colour coding throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border Multi casualty incidents?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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MINIMUM DATA SET SEM (E.WP5-5), INITIAL METHANE ALERT (E.WP5-7)

- 19. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the data transmitted in the exercise are appropriate for the proper management of victims by an emergency medical service in Multi casualty incidents?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 20. Do you think that the information conveyed in the initial incident statement test is appropriate for the needs of an emergency service in the first moments of an MCI or disaster?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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SIGRUN INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCEDURE (E.WP5-6)

- 21. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the proposed VALKYRIES project solution SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between the different health services involved in the response to a Multi casualty incident?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 22. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the tested operative procedure would allow you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 23. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the tested procedure would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to a Multi casualty incident?**

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 24. Please rate your satisfaction as far as the preparation of the exercise is concerned (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics).**

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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EVALUATION OF THE EXERCISE

- 25. Please rate your satisfaction on the training you received for the use of the proposed VALKYRIES technological solutions for the exercise.**

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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- 26. To what extent was the scenario of the Use Case realistic and responding to a potentially real life emergency?**

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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- 27. How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?**

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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- 28. How would you rate the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support) of the exercise?**

Excellent 5	Good 4	Moderate 3	Inadequate 2	Poor 1
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29. Overall, to what extent were you satisfied with the conduct of the exercise?

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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Thank you for your cooperation!

19. Annex E – CIMIC questionnaire results

The aim of the survey was to find out to what extent the course organisation has been created, the usefulness of the knowledge gained and the content of the materials and the satisfaction and expectations. At the end of the survey, trainees submitted their recommendations for the course.

Joint Multinational CIMIC Course was tested and validated during the UC3. The presentation included the course content, methodology, course objectives. In addition, two of the lectures were presented to the military cadets and officers of the National Military University. During the exercise, 17 people - military cadets and officers - were surveyed. Two answer sheets were invalid. Based on these results, some general conclusions were drawn. Here you can find the results of the survey, with the number of responses and the percentage shown below

1. To what extent does the content of the learning materials in the course correspond to your expectations? Please specify mandatory your torment

I can't judge	Does not match	There are inconsistencies	It pretty much matches	Corresponds completely
-	-	1 (6.25%)	3 (18.75%)	12 (75%)

Conclusion: The content of the learning materials in a **very large extent meets the expectations** of the trainees.

2. How do you rate the following elements in the course?

Criterion	It's missing	Low	Average	Rather high	Very high
2.1. Relevance of knowledge	-	-	-	1 (6.25%)	15 (93.75%)
2. 2. Logical connection between individual parts	-	-	-	2 (12.5%)	14 (87.5%)
2.3. Practical orientation	-	-	1 (6.25%)	4 (25%)	9 (56.25)

Conclusion: The relevance of the knowledge and the logical connection between the individual parts **are extremely high**, in addition, the learning process is practically oriented in a **very large extent**.

3. Level of carrying out of:

Criterion	Weak	Average	Good	Very good	Excellent
Teaching methodology	-	-	1 (6.25%)	7 (43.75)	8 (50%)
Visualization of learning content	-	-	1 (6.25%)	4 (25%)	11 (68.75%)
Duration of the course	-	1 (6.25%)	2 (12.5%)	5 (31.25)	8 (50%)
Organization of the course	-	-	1 (6.25%)	5 (31.25)	10 (62.5%)

Conclusion: The teaching methodology and presentation of the learning content are **at very high level**, besides the duration and organization of the course are rated **very satisfactorily**.

4. Please indicate your personal opinion which lectures and discussions were useful and why?

All lectures, and especially presented Lecture 1 and Lecture 5, are appreciated as useful for the trainees.

5. In your opinion, are you able to apply the presented materials and knowledge in your direct work?

Yes	No
15 (93.75%)	1 (6.25%)

Conclusion: In general, the materials presented and the knowledge and skills acquired **will be applied in the future work** of the trainees.

6. Would you personally recommend your colleagues to take part in this course?

Yes	No
16 (100%)	-

Conclusion: Without a doubt, the respondents would recommend their colleagues to participate in this course.

7. Please give your overall rating for the course:

Weak - 2	Satisfactory – 3	Good - 4	Very good - 5	Excellent - 6
The course is ineffective and does not achieve its goal	The course is not well organized and takes place with gaps	The course is organized and takes place with some gaps	The course is very well organized and provides good training	The course is perfectly organized and provides excellent opportunities and prospects for realization
-	-	1 (6.25%)	12 (75%)	3 (18.75%)

Conclusion: The overall evaluation of the course is more than positive - very good and excellent, which allows us to consider that **it successfully passes the testing and validation** at this stage.

8. Please give your recommendations and opinions to improve the course

The respondents made several recommendations, and they are related **to increasing the duration of the course, implementing teamwork activities and taking place in many countries** in the European Union.

General Conclusion: The overall evaluation of the course is more than positive - very good and excellent rates for relevance of knowledge, logical connection between individual parts, teaching methodology and organization of the course. Some parts of the curriculum, as duration of the course and practical orientation of the knowledge and skills could be put under the consideration. As a whole, very positive appreciation allows to consider that **it successfully passes the testing and validation** at this stage.

20. Annex G – Agenda for UC3 execution

MINISTRY OF DEFENCE OF THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA

DEFENCE INSTITUTE “PROFESSOR TSVETAN LAZAROV”

AGENDA

for UC3 execution on the H-2020 project
“Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated
procedures for First Aid Vehicles Deployment on European multi-victim Disasters”
(VALKYRIES)

10.06.2023, Saturday (*Medite Hotel, Conference room*)

14.00 Arrival of the Bulgarian team and accommodation

14.00 – 14.30 Registration and welcome coffee

14.30 – 17.30 Coordination meeting of the Bulgarian team (Participants: BDI, Bulgarian Military Medical Academy, Fire Brigade, Regional Police Department, Municipality of Sandanski and the representative of the EAB from AFCEA)

20.00 Dinner

11.06.2023, Sunday

10.00 – 18.00 (*On site and in conference room*)

- **Setting up UC3 testing sites** (OHQ, Field operations command post, Medical triage posts, deployment of equipment, checking the communications, internet, exercise implementation plan, transportation plan, logistics plan, security plan, coordination among participating institutions).
- Lunch in the hotel between 13.00 and 14.30 and two coffee breaks (morning and afternoon).
- Training of first responders to use TASSICA 3 Triage card – 07.00- 08.00 p.m. (*conference room*).

20.00 Dinner

12.06.2023, Monday (*On site*)

10.00 – 10.20 (Sandanski Sports Centre)

Opening remarks:

- Colonel Assoc. Prof. DSc. Borislav Genov, Director of the Bulgarian Defence Institute “Prof. Tsvetan Lazarov”.
- Mr Atanas Stoyanov, Mayor of the Municipality of Sandanski.

10.20 – 14.00

- The UC3 execution in the **traditional way** according to the detailed implementation plan for execution of the exercise.
- Lunch on site between 14.00 and 15.00 and coffee/refreshments.

15.00 – 18.00

- Setting-up and testing SIGRUN Integration Platform (*Sandanski Sports Centre*).
- Meeting of the Bulgarian and Greek coordination team, preparation for the testing of the VALKYRIES solution (*Medite Hotel, Conference room*), one Coffee break.

20.30 Reception on behalf of the Mayor of the Municipality of Sandanski (*Hotel Spartak*)

13.06.2023, Tuesday

10.00 – 17.30 (Conference room, Medite Hotel)

Training of first responders to use VALKYRIES tools envisaged to be demonstrated and tested in UC3 and demonstration of the training courses:

- Presentation of VALKYRIES prioritised harmonisation opportunities for validation in UC3 (WP4 – INDRA, WP5- TASSICA, WP6 - BDI);
- INDRA: iSAFTY Application Modules for C2;
- PARTICLE: Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP);
- TASSICA: Wearables/bracelets;
- ARATOS and BlockChain2050 bracelet Tap2SOS;
- BDI and Military Medical Academy: Demonstration of the Joint Multinational First Responders Training Curriculum and content;
- BDI: Demonstration of the Basic Training Curriculum for Joint CIMIC Training Programme;
- AREU: Demonstration of the Minimum set of competencies for volunteers;
- TASSICA: EU structured repository of emergency response plans.

Lunch in the hotel between 13.00 and 14.30 and two coffee breaks.

20.00 Dinner

14.06.2023, Wednesday

10.00 – 10.30 (*Sandanski Sports Centre*)

Opening remarks:

- Colonel Assoc. Prof. DSc. Borislav Genov, Director of the Bulgarian Defence Institute “Prof. Tsvetan Lazarov”.
- Mr Atanas Stoyanov, Mayor of the Municipality of Sandanski.
- Representative of the General Directorate “Fire Safety and Protection of Population” – Bulgarian Ministry of Interior.

10.30 – 14.30: UC3 execution applying the VALKYRIES solution in accordance to the detailed implementation plan.

Lunch on site between 14.30 and 15.30 and coffee/refreshments

15.30 – 16.30: After-action review (*Medite Hotel, Conference room*), one Coffee break.

16.30 – 18.30: Cultural event (*Visit to the town of Melnk*).

20.30 Dinner.

15.06.2023, Thursday (*Medite Hotel, Conference room*).

10.00 – 13.30: After action review, feedback questionnaire, preliminary evaluation of UC3 & lessons learned.

11.00 – 11.30 Coffee break.

13.30 -14.30 Lunch.

After 14.30 Departure of the participants.

21. Annex H – Evidences

21.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

Figure 15 – GLOBAL_COP: UC3 global view of the assets (Vehicles) in the field

ID	Name	Type	Status	Location	Address	Category
PATROL UNIT 1 - POLICE 1 511	SNAT Officer	Police	Available	Lat:44.015434, 23.2786	BPD - Shapovgrad (POLICE)	LOCAL POLICE Sandanski
PATROL UNIT 2	Law Enforcement Patrol Unit	Police	Available	Lat:44.02 3886, 24.8943	BPD - Shapovgrad (POLICE)	LOCAL POLICE Sandanski
PATROL UNIT 1	Law Enforcement Patrol Unit	Police	Available	Lat:44.02 3886, 24.8943	BPD - Shapovgrad (POLICE)	LOCAL POLICE Sandanski
VOLUNTEER 3 716	Crisis Intervention Specialist	Volunteer	Available	Lat:44.01 5716, 23.2853	Municipality of Sandanski	VOLUNTEERS UNIT
VOLUNTEER 4 714	Crisis Intervention Specialist	Volunteer	Available	Lat:44.01 5716, 23.2853	Municipality of Sandanski	VOLUNTEERS UNIT
VOLUNTEER 3 713	Crisis Intervention Specialist	Volunteer	Available	Lat:44.01 5716, 23.2853	Municipality of Sandanski	VOLUNTEERS UNIT
VOLUNTEER 3 710	Crisis Intervention Specialist	Volunteer	Available	Lat:44.01 5716, 23.2853	Municipality of Sandanski	VOLUNTEERS UNIT
VOLUNTEER 1 711	Crisis Intervention Specialist	Volunteer	Available	Lat:44.01 5716, 23.2853	Municipality of Sandanski	VOLUNTEERS UNIT
MNI BUS - MUNICIPALITY	Bus	Bus	Available	Lat:44.015716, 23.2853	Municipality of Sandanski	VOLUNTEERS UNIT
AMB - DRIVER - TRAGE 2 238	Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015677, 23.2820	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
CADETE DOCTOR 3 - TRAGE 2 225	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015624, 23.2793	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
CADETE DOCTOR 2 - TRAGE 2 224	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015624, 23.2793, 2181	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
CADETE DOCTOR 1 - TRAGE 2 223	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015627, 23.2820	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
ML DOCTOR 2 222	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015627, 23.2820	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
ML DOCTOR 1 221	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015627, 23.2820	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
AMBULANCE	Ambulance, Advance Life Support (Ground)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015627, 23.2820	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 2 - FLOODS
Driver 214	Emergency Vehicle Operator	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015434, 23.2786	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 1 - EARTH-Q
Cadet Doctor 2 213	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015434, 23.2786	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 1 - EARTH-Q
Cadet Doctor 1 212	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015434, 23.2786	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 1 - EARTH-Q
Support (radiology) 211	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015434, 23.2786	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 1 - EARTH-Q
BUS TRAGE 1	Bus	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015627, 23.2820	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	Medical Triage Unit 1 - EARTH-Q
RMU Doctor 2 202	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 9027, 23.2703	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	MMA - Response Medical Unit
RMU Doctor 1 201	Advanced Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 9027, 23.2703	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	MMA - Response Medical Unit
RMU - AMBULANCE 2	Ambulance, Advance Life Support (Ground)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6927, 23.2708	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	MMA - Response Medical Unit
RMU - AMBULANCE 1	Ambulance, Advance Life Support (Ground)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6926, 23.2706	Military Medical Academy (MMA)	MMA - Response Medical Unit
St. Vasilko DOCTOR 2 812	Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6716, 28.3803	St. Vasilko HOSPITAL	EMS
St. Vasilko DOCTOR 1 811	Emergency Medical Technician	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6716, 28.3803	St. Vasilko HOSPITAL	EMS
HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	Ambulance, Advance Life Support (Ground)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.015702, 23.2803	St. Vasilko HOSPITAL	EMS
HELI - Search Operator 2 818	Aircraft, Transport AirBays Air Bags (special equipment)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6534, 23.2789	BULGAVY AIR FORCE	20th Helicopter Air Base
HELI - Search Operator 1 814	Aircraft, Transport AirBays Air Bags (special equipment)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6534, 23.2789	BULGAVY AIR FORCE	20th Helicopter Air Base
HELI - Crew Member 2 813	Aircraft, Transport AirBays Air Bags (special equipment)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6534, 23.2789	BULGAVY AIR FORCE	20th Helicopter Air Base
HELI - Crew Member 2 812	Aircraft, Transport AirBays Air Bags (special equipment)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6534, 23.2789	BULGAVY AIR FORCE	20th Helicopter Air Base
HELI - Crew Member 1 811	Aircraft, Transport AirBays Air Bags (special equipment)	Medical	Available	Lat:44.01 6534, 23.2789	BULGAVY AIR FORCE	20th Helicopter Air Base
HELICOPTER 1	Aircraft, Rotary Wing	Medical	Available	Lat:44.02 3886, 24.8943	BULGAVY AIR FORCE	20th Helicopter Air Base

Figure 16 – GLOBAL_COP: Example of the UC3 assets list status and their location

Figure 17 – GLOBAL_COP: UC3 global view of victims' transportation status and global figures

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Multi Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History	Incident	By Unit
TAS50022 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMAK - Special Unit for disasters
TAS50009 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	32 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50016 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50036 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	66 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [lower extremity]	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50018 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50011 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	17 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMAK - Special Unit for disasters
TAS50019 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	17 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50008 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	60 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [head/neck]	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMAK - Special Unit for disasters
TAS50040 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	30 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [lower extremity]	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50056 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ELDER	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Flood	HBT1 1311
TAS50010 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	20 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMAK - Special Unit for disasters
TAS50065 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50009 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	26 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [head/neck]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50014 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50016 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	26 / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [lower extremity]	RNU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Flood	HBT1 1311
TAS50001 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50012 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50030 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	65 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [head/neck]	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMAK - Special Unit for disasters
TAS50048 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	17 / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Flood	HBT1 1311
TAS50017 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA [abdomen/pelvis]	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	FSS_Bulg_1022
TAS50002 II	2023-06-16 10:21:46	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMAK - Special Unit for disasters

Figure 18 – GLOBAL_COP: UC3 global view of victims' triage status (first and second), triage data, Destination, assigned transportation

21.2. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication

UC3 overview catastrophe is a cross-border crisis as an earthquake result in the border area between Bulgaria and Greece, causing a series of humanitarian crises and industrial accidents threatening the lives of the population in the Bulgarian-Greek border area. Many elements were deployed to assist affected population in the cross-border area, humanitarian aid and restoring family links. Four Missions were created so far before 14/06/2023 10:31. To provide logistical support and coordination many assets have been activated.

Mission	Agency	Status	Mission type	Created date/Planned start date	Planned end date
IN/0000289[1]	112	Active	Scouting Mission	14/06/2023 10:17	
IN/0000289[2]	112	Active	Control	14/06/2023 10:18	
IN/0000289[3]	112	Active	Control	14/06/2023 10:19	
IN/0000289[4]	112	Active	Medical Support	14/06/2023 10:31	

Unit element					
Element	Unit	Type	Mission	Status	
UNIT 1 - FDFSCP-Sandanski	BFSP	Earthquake	IN/0000289[1]		
UNIT 1 - Local Police department - Sandanski	BP	Earthquake	IN/0000289[2]		
UNIT 5 - FDFSCP-Blagoevgrad	BFSP	Earthquake	IN/0000289[3]		
UNIT 4 - SOA- Blagoevgrad	BFSP	Earthquake	IN/0000289[3]		
UNIT 3 - SOA- Blagoevgrad	BFSP	Earthquake	IN/0000289[3]		
Volunteer Unit	MoS	Earthquake	IN/0000289[3]		
4th EMAK- Special Unit for Disasters	HFS	Earthquake	IN/0000289[3]		
Medical Triage Unit 2	BMA	Earthquake	IN/0000289[4]		
EMS Hosp. St Vrach	BEAS	Earthquake	IN/0000289[4]		

Figure 19 – iSafety Command and Control: element window

In the Unit element control, the viewer can check the whole transport fleet. The platform collects the entire set of emergency vehicles as well as the relevant data.

Unit	Element	Type	Control group	Location	Element status	Mission	Type	Location	Date	Assign status
BFSP	CRWT02	CRWT - Crew Transport	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[3]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
BFSP	FT01	FTR - Fire Truck	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[1]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
MoS	YU	MBUS - Mini Bus	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[3]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
BP	LPD01	PTU - Patrol Unit	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[2]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
BMA	MTU02	AMB - Ambulance	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[4]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
BEAS	AMB01	AMB - Ambulance	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[4]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
BFSP	VHC01	VHC - Vehicle	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[3]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
BFSP	CRWT01	CRWT - Crew Transport	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Active	IN/0000289[3]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
HFS	4EMAK	CRWT - Crew Transport	GA LUME	41.374° N, 23.369° E	Active	IN/0000289[3]	Geological - Earthquake	41.552° N, 23.272° E	10:18	
HFS	2EMAK	CRWT - Crew Transport	GA LUME	41.374° N, 23.369° E	Available					
HRT	USAR	BUS - Bus	GA LUME	41.374° N, 23.369° E	Available					
HNCA	ETIK	VHC - Vehicle	GA LUME	41.374° N, 23.369° E	Available					
BFSP	FF01	VHC - Vehicle	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Available					
BFSP	HLC01	HLP - Helicopter	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.172° E	Available					
BMA	MTU01	AMB - Ambulance	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Available					
BP	LPD02	PTU - Patrol Unit	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Available					
HRT	WRT	BUS - Bus	GA LUME	41.374° N, 23.369° E	Available					
BEAS	AMB02	AMB - Ambulance	GA LUME	41.552° N, 23.272° E	Available					

Figure 20 – iSafety: Unit Element control window

22. Annex J – WP4 Result sheets

22.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

22.1.1. CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest vehicles

CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest vehicles			
Description	The system MUST be able to generate an updated vehicles position picture that support the Operational Command to make better time dependent victims evacuation decisions.		
Location/Participants	Location: Bulgaria. Participants: PARTICLE, BDI, Indra, Bulgarian Emergency ambulance services, Bulgarian military unit		
Requirements	REQ_BASE_T4.1_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_7, REQ_COM_T4.5_2, REQ_COM_T4.5_9, REQ_COM_T4.5_10, REQ_COM_T4.5_11, REQ_COM_T4.5_15		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Vehicles position elapsed time between the real position and the information updated in the command centre: < 2 minute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vehicles position know at the command centre - Vehicles position updates within a gape time bellow 2 minutes - Vehicles destination capable of estimating a vehicle ETA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KPI 1: Information available (Success) - KPI 2: Updated position of vehicles (Success) - KPI 3: time elapsed (Success) 	Demo
	Description	Information confidentiality	
	Participants	PARTICLE / Bulgarian Emergency ambulance services, Bulgarian military unit	
	Location	Simulated Border Bulgaria-Greece / Sandanski city	
	Execution	To verify the vehicles and actors' position, correctly reported and presented and GLOBAL COP.	
	Analysis and results	The result of this test is the verification that the vehicles' location is correctly reported and updated within an acceptable time and disseminated to the User within an acceptable elapsed time. Improved response time compared to previous UC.	

CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest vehicles		
		Vehicle on water (boat) was included in the demo for the first time.
	History of corrective measures	Backbone DB was optimized to run faster.
	Lessons learned	Bracelets generation of victim ID worked ok although the ID tags needs to be harmonized.
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	(See enquiry from UC3)
	Result	YES

Table 20 – Results sheet CO-WP4-15-T01

22.2. CO-WP4-42- Reduce Voice Communication

22.2.1. CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	<i>Integration test related to Incident Creation, Task Creation and assets creation and update for UC3</i>		
Location/Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Testing Sessions remotely: 26^h May, 2nd June (Indra, Tassica, Particle)</i> • <i>Final session Testing remotely 9th June (Indra, Tassica Particle)</i> • <i>Demo Testing: 12nd June (Sandanski, Tassica, BDI, Indra, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Final Demo: 14th June (Sandanski, BDI, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, Bulgarian Fire Brigade, Hellenic Fire Brigade, Bulgarian Emergency ambulance Service, HRT, Areu)</i> 		
Requirements	REQ_COM-T4.3.2, REQ_COM-T4.3.10, REQ_COM-T4.3.19, REQ_COM-T4.3.22		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method

CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication

<p>1.Incident Reported in SIGRUN 2.Task Reported in SIGRUN 3.Asset assignment to task in incident is reported in SIGRUN 4.Asset status is reported in SIGRUN 5.Asset location is reported in SIGRUN 6. GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices</p>	<p>iSafety application updates data in SIGRUN GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets) DATA AND METADATA logging is visualized on secured blockchain networks visible by authorized users</p>	<p>KPI 1: Information about the incident available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 2: information about the task available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 3: Information about assets localization available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 4. Information about assets associated to tasks is available in SIGRUN. YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 5. Information related to Incident/tasks/assets in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	<p>Test</p>
	<p>Description</p>	<p>Incident Creation for UC3</p>	
	<p>Participants</p>	<p>Indra, Particle</p>	
	<p>Location</p>	<p>Remotly/OnSite</p>	
	<p>Execution</p>	<p>Step-by-step description of how the verification test was run.</p>	
	<p>Analysis and results</p>	<p>Description of the procedure for collecting results, its analytical actions (if necessary) and the general results achieved.</p>	
	<p>History of corrective measures</p>	<p>If the verification initially failed, this cell describes the different corrective actions to fit expectations.</p>	
	<p>Lessons learned</p>	<p>It highlights the difficulties suffered, and any possible conclusions or lessons learned to be considered in the later stages of development.</p>	
	<p>Quality</p>	<p>A</p>	
	<p>End-user feedback</p>	<p>No end user feedback.</p>	
	<p>Result</p>	<p>YES</p>	

Table 21 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T01

Below is a more detailed test with the complete exercise. The verification steps are repeated depending on the missions, tasks and resources that are managed from command and control.

TEST-ID	CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication				
Location	Remotly				
Date					
Participants	INDRA				
ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Incident Creation	Incident 1	EARTHQUAKE		Incident Creation 10:00h (BULGARIA)	OK
Incident Creation	Incident 2	EARTHQUAKE		Incident Creation 10:00h (GREECE)	OK
Incident Creation	Incident 3	FLOOD		Incident Creation 10:45h (BULGARIA)	OK
Incident Creation	Incident 4	FLOOD		Incident Creation 10:45h (GREECE)	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	SCOUTING	Incident 1	Scouting 10:10h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	FIRE TRUCK	"ON THE WAY"	Fire truck on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	FIRE TRUCK	"ON SITE"	Fire truck on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	CONTROL	Incident 1	Control Task 10:10h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	POLICE CAR	"ON THE WAY"	Police car on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	POLICE CAR	"ON SITE"	Police car on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 3	CONTROL	Incident 1	Control Task 10:25h Sport Center	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	VEHICLE	"ON THE WAY"	Vehicle on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	VEHICLE	"ON SITE"	Vehicle on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 3	CONTROL	Incident 1	Control Task 10:35h Collapsed Building	OK

TEST-ID	CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication				
Location	Remotly				
Date					
Participants	INDRA				
ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Asset Update	Mission 3	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON THE WAY"	Crew transport on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON SITE"	Crew transport on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 3	CONTROL	Incident 1	Control Task 10:35h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON THE WAY"	Crew transport on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON SITE"	Crew transport on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 4	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 1	Medical Support task 11:05h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	Medical Triaje on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	Medical Triaje on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 4	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 1	Medical Support task 11:05h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	EMS on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	EMS on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	SCOUTING	Incident 3	Scouting 12:35h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	VEHICLE	"ON THE WAY"	Vehicle on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	VEHICLE	"ON SITE"	Vehicle on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	CONTROL	Incident 3	Control Task 12:35h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	POLICE CAR	"ON THE WAY"	Police car on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	POLICE CAR	"ON SITE"	Police car on site	OK

TEST-ID	CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication				
Location	Remotly				
Date					
Participants	INDRA				
ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Mission Creation	Mission 3	CONTROL	Incident 3	Control Task 11:30h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	HELICOPTER	"ON THE WAY"	Helicopter on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 3	HELICOPTER	"ON SITE"	Helicopter on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 4	CONTROL	Incident 3	Control Task 12:35h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	BUS	"ON THE WAY"	Medical triaje on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 4	BUS	"ON SITE"	Medical triaje on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	SCOUTING	Incident 2	Scouting 11:05h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	BUS	"ON THE WAY"	Medical triaje on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	BUS	"ON SITE"	Medical triaje on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 5	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 3	Medical Support task 12:40h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AMBULANCE	"ON THE WAY"	EMS on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	AMBULANCE	"ON SITE"	EMS on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 5	MEDICAL SUPPORT	Incident 3	Medical Support task 12:40h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	MINI BUS	"ON THE WAY"	Volunteer Unit on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 5	MINI BUS	"ON SITE"	Volunteer Unit on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	CONTROL	Incident 4	Control Task 12:40h Struma River	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	BUS	"ON THE WAY"	Water Rescue Department on the way	OK

TEST-ID	CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication				
Location	Remotly				
Date					
Participants	INDRA				
ACTION		TYPE (Isafety)		Description	Results
Asset Update	Mission 1	BUS	"ON SITE"	Water Rescue Department on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	CONTROL	Incident 2	Control Task 11:05h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	VEHICLE	"ON THE WAY"	ETIK on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	POLICE CAR	"ON SITE"	ETIK on site	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	CONTROL	Incident 2	Control Task 11:05h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON THE WAY"	Helenic Fire Service on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON SITE"	Helenic Fire Service on the way	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	CONTROL	Incident 2	Control Task 11:05h Collapsed Building	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON THE WAY"	Helenic Fire Service on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	CREW TRANSPORT	"ON SITE"	Helenic Fire Service on the way	OK
Incident close	Incident 1	EARTHQUAKE		Close incident (BULGARIA)	OK
Incident close	Incident 2	EARTHQUAKE		Close incident (GREECE)	OK
Incident close	Incident 3	FLOOD		Close incident (BULGARIA)	OK
Incident close	Incident 4	FLOOD		Close incident (GREECE)	OK

Table 22 – Detailed test CO-WP4-42-T01

22.2.2. CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	<i>Integration Test related to Triage Information (UC3), the information should be the same in both countries and different devices</i>		
Date and Location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Testing Sessions remotely: 26th May, 2nd June (Indra, Tassica, Particle)</i> • <i>Final session Testing remotely 9th June (Indra, Tassica Particle)</i> • <i>Demo Testing: 12nd June (Sandanski, Tassica, BDI, Indra, SUMMA)</i> • <i>Final Demo: 14th June (Sandanski, BDI, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, Bulgarian Fire Brigade, Hellenic Fire Brigade, Bulgarian Emergency ambulance Service, HRT, Areu)</i> 		
Participants	<i>BDI, SUMMA, Indra, Particle, Tassica, Bulgarian Fire Brigade, Hellenic Fire Brigade, Bulgarian Emergency ambulance Service, HRT, Areu</i>		
Requirements	<i>COM_T4.3_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_22, REQ_COM_T4.4_10, REQ_COM_T4.4_11, REQ_COM_T4.5.2.</i>		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<p>1. <i>Victims registration in SIGRUN</i></p> <p>2. <i>Victims' status time update in SIGRUN</i></p> <p>3. <i>Victims triage data update in SIGRUN</i></p> <p>4. <i>GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices</i></p> <p>5. <i>GLOBAL COP information accessible in different countries</i></p>	<p><i>System applications updates incident data in SIGRUN</i></p> <p><i>Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN</i></p> <p><i>GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets)</i></p> <p><i>GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in both countries</i></p>	<p>KPI 1: <i>Victim Registration available: YES/NO (Available = success)</i></p> <p>KPI 2: <i>Victim status time update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success)</i></p> <p>KPI 3: <i>Victims triage data update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success)</i></p> <p>KPI 4: <i>Information related Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success)</i></p> <p>KPI 5: <i>Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)</i></p>	Test
Verification action #1	Description	<i>Victim Registration and Medical Information Registration Verification</i>	

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication		
	Execution	<i>Incident (Earthquake) is created into SIGRUN Platform Victim Age/Gender is registered in the platform. Status Triage information is updated (AT, ET) Main Pathology is updated Triage Classification is updated Transport is updated Staff reporting information is available</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The terminals (mobile phones) must be setup for staff information. Connectivity with URL and API must be configured and checked previously. 4G communication must be ensured.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The communications and access to URL/API for terminals and applications deployed with GLOBAL COP must be checked before and the application for digitalizing triage process must be checked in every terminal before to avoid problems during the test We must ensure that the application starts with the user/password indicated and that the screens with the maps load correctly.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No feed Back from user
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>GLOBAL COP Information visualized in TABLET and the same for both countries</i>
	Execution	<i>We check that the same information displayed in workstation is displayed in GLOBAL COP and the workstations from Command Post for each country</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in a tablet GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The terminals must be setup for staff information.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The communications and access to API/URL must be checked before the test. We must verify that the GLOBAL COP is displayed in the browser before testing (Specific URL for UC)</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No feed Back from user
Result	YES	

Table 23 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T02

22.2.3. CO-WP4-42_T03- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	Test for Verification Real Time Update in SIGRUN Platform (UC3)		
Date and Location	Final Demo: 14th June (Sandanski)		
Participants	BDI, SUMMA, INDRA, Particle, Tassica, Bulgarian Fire Brigade, Hellenic Fire Brigade, Bulgarian Emergency ambulance Service, HRT, Areu		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T4.3.1		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<p>1. Incident reported in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>2.Task Registration in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>3.Assets registration in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>4. Assets update in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p>	<p>System applications update data in SIGRUN</p> <p>Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN</p>	<p>KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database) < 60 sec 100% success Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success > 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database) < 60 sec 100% success Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success > 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database) < 60 sec 100% success Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success > 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 4: Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	Test

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication		
Verification action #1	Description	<i>Incident Creation</i>
	Execution	<i>Incident (Earthquake) is created into SIGRUN Platform by an operator</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We verify that we have the isafety logs and that we have the information in the SIGRUN database for subsequent analysis.</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The same that previous tests CO-WP4-42_T01</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The same that previous tests CO-WP4-42_T01</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>Task Creation</i>
	Execution	<i>A task (Scouting Mission) is created into the incident</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We verify that we have the isafety logs and that we have the information in the SIGRUN database for subsequent analysis.</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The same that previous tests CO-WP4-42_T01</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The same that previous tests CO-WP4-42_T01</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES
Verification action #3	Description	<i>Asset assignment to a Task</i>
	Execution	<i>An asset is attached to the previous task created (Fire Unit)</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We ensure that we have the application logs locally and the data in the central DB for further analysis.</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The same that previous tests CO-WP4-42_T01</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The environment is the same as the previous tests and we can extract the same lessons.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES

Table 24 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T03

22.3. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platform

22.3.1. CO-WP4-21- T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

CO-WP4-21- T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms			
Description	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data form multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.		
Location/Participants	UMU		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T7.2_1, REQ_COM_T7.2_2, REQ_COM_T7.2_3		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Creation of a model which can speed up tasks in an emergency response.	Execution time: Time prediction – less than 1000ms. System resource consumption: Imperceptible	KPI 1: Adequacy: 90%. KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: less than 5000ms	Demo
	Description	Data analysis	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	<i>As the test CO-WP4-42- T03 is successful, to demonstrate this requirement, the database with the gathered data during use cases by different sources of different first responders have been checked to analyse the data generated and apply pre-processed techniques to the data and create trained models.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Different data processing techniques have been applied to obtain the most important features, and then three Machine Learning models have been generated. The first one consists of predicting the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one. The second model predicts the patient's death after the first triage. The last model predicts the patient's worsening after the first triage. All information about the processing techniques and the generated models can be found in D.7.2.</i>	
	History of corrective measures		
	Lessons learned	<i>Analysing triage data generated in different use cases and creating predictive models is highly important for first responders to obtain patterns and trends that may go unnoticed.</i>	
	Quality	A	
	End-user feedback	<i>No end user feedback.</i>	
Result	YES		

Table 25 – Results sheet CO-WP4-21-T01

23. Annex K – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

23.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION			
Description	<p>The prototype VALKYRIES Collaborative Glossary for Emergency Response Planning, Preparedness and Execution (VALKYRIES GLOSSARY) has provided a common understanding of terms for VALKYRIES researchers and all partners involved in the planning and execution of demonstrators. It has also served as a fundamental reference for the development of the SIGRUN federated system.</p> <p>On the CU working days, prior to the MCI exercise, a questionnaire was developed to gather the opinions of those involved in the in organisational tasks of the UC3. (VERIFICATION ACTION #1).</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_2 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Importance of all emergency services using a unified glossary to plan and respond to MCI and disasters	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by respondents.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC3 previous tasks.	
	Description	<p>A questionnaire was performed to evaluate the acceptance of a unified glossary for UC3 planning, preparedness and execution. Question 1 of the survey is related to this enabler.</p> <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>	
	Execution	<p>The consultation took place during the UC3 workdays, before the execution of the MCI drill.</p> <p>The survey was addressed to all participants from all institutions that have used the VALKYRIES GLOSSARY for Emergency Planning, Preparedness and Response in their tasks of preparing the UC.</p>	

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION		
Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following result was obtained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Importance: 93,75% (ACHIEVED) • Predominant response: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT 	
History of corrective measures		
Lessons learned		
Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).	
End-user feedback		
Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 26 – Results sheet CO.WP5-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K, section WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence (evidence 1 and 3, question 1)

23.2. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

VALKYRIES Project proposes two enablers to achieve harmonisation and pre-standardisation in the field of MCI operating procedures:

- Unification of triage with regard to priorities and casualty labelling codes in MCI and disasters.
- Standardised triage card TASSICA 3 as a non-technological tool to support traceability, unified prioritisation, interoperability and labelling of victims.

Both have been tested and evaluated in the UC3.

23.2.1. CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>The VALKYRIES project proposes a EU-wide standardised a pentapolar triage code, based primarily on NATO standards, to unify the coding and labelling of casualties in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters.</p> <p>The assessment of the enabler in the UC3 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed in the UC3 workdays to collect respondents' opinions on the standardized coding and classifying victims proposed by VALKYRIES Project in the UC (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • The degree of compliance of the UCs implementation with the VALKYRIES recommendations regarding the standardised classification and coding (colour) of victims was verified on the basis

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
	<p>of the data stored in the SIGRUN federated system during the UC drill (VERIFICATION ACTION #2).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finally, an online survey was conducted at the end of the UC drill to collect participants' evaluation (VERIFICATION ACTION #3). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Stakeholder coding and labelling agreement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Cross-border cooperation improvement: The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION

and coding system.			
UC coding standardisation compliance: The degree of adherence in the UC to the standardised classification and coding of MCI victims proposed by VALKYRIES.	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 4: The information related to the triage of victims in SIGRUN complies with the standardised classification and coding proposed by VALKYRIES.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Description	<p>A survey was carried out containing questions (2, 3, and 4) regarding the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of EMS using the same classification to designate triage priority in MCI and disasters. • Use of a specific name for triage priorities • Specific assignment of colours for different triage priorities. • Assessment of the use of the same classification and colour coding in the EU to facilitate EMS working together in cross-border MCI. <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>	
	Execution	<p>During the UC3 workdays, all training sessions with responders worked with the pentapolar classification proposed by VALKYRIES for the coding and labelling of triage priorities for mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters. At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the training actions were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis.</p>	
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 96,88% (ACHIEVED) 	

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 87,50% (ACHIEVED) KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevance: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Cross-border cooperation improvement: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	<i>"I think that the blue category it's no needed."</i>
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 14 June 2023.
	Participants	Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece), Hellenic National Center for Emergency Assistance – EKAB (Greece), Hellenic Fire Service (Greece), Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (Sofia, Bulgaria), Sandanski Municipality Volunteers Unit (Bulgaria), Military Medical Academy (Bulgaria).
	Description	The degree of compliance with the proposed standardised classification and coding (colour) of victims during the UC has been assessed on the basis of the data recorded in SIGRUN during the conduct of UC3 drill.
	Execution	A cross-national MCI exercise was carried out with the participation of various emergency services assuming the different roles involved in the emergency response (first responders, disaster managers, technologists, etc.). The information related to victims' triage coding was created and shared by first responders through SIGRUN. The identification data and pathology of the drill victims were fictitious. Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform will be verified prior to the test. The terminals will be previously configured with the associated users.
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 4: Coding compliance: YES (ACHIEVED) <p>All categories and colour codes used to indicate the triage priority of victims in the various SIGRUN federated tools used in UC3 have been aligned with the triage categories and codes proposed by VALKYRIES.</p>
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 15 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC3 drill.
	Description	<p>After the UC3, an extensive online survey was conducted to gather the participants' assessment of various aspects of the UC3, in relation to the various VALKYRIES enablers brought to the demonstrator, and in relation to the organisation and development of the use case itself.</p> <p>Some of these questions (15, 16, 17 and 18) asked about topics such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The significance of EMS employing a uniform classification for triage prioritization in MCIs and disasters. Adoption of a unified labelling for triage levels. Dedicated colour allocations for each triage priority. <p>Evaluation of the adoption of consistent classification and colour coding across the EU to aid EMS collaboration during cross-border MCIs.</p>
	Execution	<p>This evaluation was carried out in coordination with other VALKYRIES enablers, using the SIGRUN platform as integration tool, in the same drill detailed for VERIFICATION ACTION #2.</p> <p>The simulation worked with the pentapolar classification proposed by VALKYRIES for the coding and labelling of triage priorities in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters.</p> <p>At the end of the drill, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey voluntarily and anonymously. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:

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		<p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 90,70% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 86,30% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 86% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: STRONGLY AGREE • Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: STRONGLY AGREE • Cross-border cooperation improvement: STRONGLY AGREE
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 27 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance

See Annex K, section WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 1 and 3 (questions 2, 3 and 4)
- Evidence 6

See Annex C – Results from feedback survey with first responders (Frequency tables), questions 15, 16, 17 and 18.

23.2.2. CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>VALKYRIES proposes the use of a standardised triage card (TASSICA 3) in the EU for the recording of key casualty information by the different emergency services that may intervene in a MCI.</p> <p>UC3 assessed the validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card as a mean of supporting interoperability between services (professional or volunteer, civilian or military), fairness in prioritising treatment, recording casualty information and traceability in mass casualty and disaster situations.</p> <p>The assessment of the enabler in the UC3 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed to collect respondents' opinions on the TASSICA 3 triage card (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • The effectiveness of this enabler was also assessed objectively in UC3 (VERIFICATION ACTION #2). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5 • Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

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scene of an MCI.			
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED)	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of	Demonstration

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders.	to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	at least 80% by stakeholders.	
Stakeholder satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

	percentage).		
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 11 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Description	<p>A questionnaire was prepared with questions (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12) on the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which the card helps to homogenise triage priorities, decide on life-saving gestures, ensure traceability of a victim, and facilitates the recording of health information. • Degree in which its use reduces the stress of healthcare staff in decision making. • Assessment of its use in facilitating joint EMS work in cross-border MCI. • Rating on enabling more efficient execution of tasks in a MCI compared to other procedures. • Overall level of satisfaction <p>The survey was open to all the First Responders involved in the exercise. The respondents answered the survey anonymously. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known. The personal details of the victims used during the simulation exercise are fictitious.</p>	
	Execution	<p>Within the development days of the UC3, a training session was carried out in relation to the operational procedure using TASSICA 3 triage card. In this session, the participants practised all the steps and roles involved in the different specific operational procedures proposed for attending to victims of an MCI or disaster.</p> <p>At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis.</p>	
Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 84,38% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 90,63% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 81,25% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 93,75% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 84,38% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Stakeholder satisfaction: 81,25% (ACHIEVED) 		

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION		
		<p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-rater reliability: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Decision-making confidence: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Traceability: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Victim information completeness and accuracy: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT First responder wellbeing: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Task execution efficiency: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Collaboration efficiency: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Stakeholder satisfaction: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	Some writing problems on the material used to make the first triage cards tested suggested that the material should be revised for future demonstrations.
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	<p><i>"I think in the field of play the size of the words will be a problem."</i></p> <p><i>"It was difficult to write in some parts of the card, mostly front page EXPOSURE and SYMPTOMS. Maybe better to write with marker instead of pen. Very analytical descriptions if you don't remember (example respiratory rate)"</i></p> <p><i>"The card's material needs some improvement, I couldn't write on it. Overall I think is a little bit complicated and needs clarification before use."</i></p> <p><i>"The TASSICA cards needs to be tested in the field in MODEX exercises and in real incidents of mass losses, in order to be considered a unseful tool for first responders and medical staff."</i></p> <p><i>"You can use more icons to be more visalised to the secondary responders and after all you can use text to fill."</i></p> <p><i>"The cards must be easy to write on in order to work well. Other then thant the card in usefull."</i></p>
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 12 June 2023.
	Participants	Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece), Hellenic National Center for Emergency Assistance – EKAB (Greece), Hellenic Fire Service (Greece), Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (Sofia, Bulgaria), Sandanski Municipality Volunteers Unit (Bulgaria), Military Medical Academy (Bulgaria).
	Description	The objective validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card was assessed on the basis of the data recorded by VALKYRIES' evaluators during the conduct of UC3 drill.

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

		A data sheet was defined to manually record the information needed to evaluate TASSICA 3 triage card during the UC execution.
Execution		<p>In UC3, a first cross-border MCI response exercise was carried out in 2 different phases, one led by the Greek emergency services and the other by the Bulgarian emergency services, although in both cases the responders from both countries worked together.</p> <p>In the exercise led by the Bulgarian services, the victims were divided into 2 foci: collapsed building and overflowing river.</p> <p>In each phase, search and rescue, triage, stabilisation and evacuation actions for MCI victims were carried out simultaneously in 2 different ways, each using a different operating procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procedure normally used in each emergency service (with each service's usual triage cards). 2. Procedure using TASSICA 3 triage cards. <p>Collection of the information necessary to evaluate the TASSICA 3 triage card was made manually by a network of VALKYRIES' evaluators. The number and location of those evaluators during the execution of the UC was defined in order to properly carry out the data collection for the evaluation of the proposed enabler.</p>
Analysis and results		<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage threshold (TASSICA 3): 48,5 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: Triage accuracy rate (TASSICA 3): 91,18% (ACHIEVED) <p>The following results were obtained using the procedures in place before the VALKYRIES proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to triage threshold: 56,32 sec • Triage accuracy rate: 88,24% <p>The TASSICA 3 Triage Card reduces the time the first responder spends on primary triage tasks by 13.85% and also achieves greater accuracy in prioritising medical care for disaster victims.</p>
History of corrective measures		
Lessons learned		
Quality		A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback		
Result		Successful verification: YES

Table 28 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K, section WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 1 and 3 (questions 5 to 12)
- Evidence 5

23.3. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
Description	<p>VALKYRIES proposes a Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) for Emergency Medical Services to share during MCIs and disasters concerning victim care. This EMS MDS includes data such as victim identification, characteristics, contact details, location, injuries, clinical updates, and other vital information.</p> <p>The assessment of this enabler in the UC3 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed in the UC workdays to collect respondents' opinions on the EMS MDS proposed by VALKYRIES Project in the UC (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • An online survey was conducted at the end of the UC drill to collect participants' evaluation on EMS MDS (VERIFICATION ACTION #2). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22 • Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 13 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Description	<p>A survey was carried out containing questions (1 and 2) related to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opinion on whether the data transmitted in the test are appropriate for the proper management of casualties by an EMS in MCI or disasters. Whether the data exchanged has been useful to complete their care tasks. 	
	Execution	<p>Within the working days of the UC3, a training session was carried out in relation to the operating procedures using SIGRUN federated system. This exercise worked with the EMS-MDS proposed by VALKYRIES for standardization of sharing information related to victims in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters. In this simulation, the participants practised all the steps and roles involved in the different specific operating procedures proposed for attending to victims of a MCI or disaster.</p> <p>At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>	
Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Data relevance: 92% (ACHIEVED) KPI 2: Data usefulness: 72% (NOT ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data relevance: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Data usefulness: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT <p>The evaluation of the selected dataset as EMS-MDS is certainly considered to be very fit for purpose. However, it is striking to what extent this dataset is considered to be less</p>		

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION		
		helpful for the first responder's own tasks. Despite the fact that 80% of positive assessments by stakeholders were not reached to overcome this indicator, 28% of respondents were indifferent, 28% were QUITE AGREED and 40% were TOTALLY AGREED. Therefore, in the opinion of the VALKYRIES researchers, the assessment of the aspect evaluated can be considered positive.
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	In general, the subjective KPIs established for the WP5 enablers have compliance criteria such that very positive results (but less than 80% of respondents with a favourable opinion) are considered as non-compliance with the KPI. As these KPIs have been defined in previous stages of the project, they will not be revised at this stage, but will be the subject of lessons learned for other future research work.
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Online survey, 15 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC3 drill.
	Description	At the end of the workdays, an online survey was conducted to gather the participants' assessment of various aspects of the UC3. One of the questions (19) asked about the suitability of the data provided during the test for EMS to effectively manage casualties in MCIs or disasters.
	Execution	A MCI simulation was deployed, with defined roles and tasks: search and rescue, C2, EMS, security, etc., each of which generates data displayed and shared in real time. The data in relation to casualties was in accordance with the EMS-MDS defined by VALKYRIES. SIGRUN was used as the information exchange system. The demonstration employed a variety of technological and software tools to support responders, as a sample, all federated in SIGRUN. At the end of the drill, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey voluntarily and anonymously. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 83,70% (ACHIEVED) • Predominant response: STRONGLY AGREE
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 29 – Results sheet CO.WP5-12-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K, section WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence (evidence 2 and 4, questions 1 and 2)

See Annex C. Results from feedback survey with first responders (Frequency tables), question 19

23.4. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>The VALKYRIES demonstrators have demonstrated SIGRUN's ability to significantly improve operational procedures related to C2, logistics, operations and medical care provided by first responders, thus facilitating a more efficient response to Mass Casualty Incidents (MCIs) or disasters. A collection of technological tools, unified under SIGRUN and integrated into the operational protocols of each of the emergency services involved in the use cases, served as an example for this UC3 demonstration and as a means to evaluate this enabler.</p> <p>The assessment of the enabler in the UC3 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed among the participants of the UC workshops to collect their opinion on the benefits of using the proposed solution, SIGRUN, integrated in their operating procedures (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • The degree of compliance with some KPIs defined for the evaluation of this VALKYRIES was verified in the UC on the basis of the data stored in the federated SIGRUN system during the simulation (VERIFICATION ACTION #2). • Finally, at the end of the exercise, an online survey was carried out among the participants to collect their opinion on the impact of using SIGRUN integrated in their operating procedures (VERIFICATION ACTION #3).

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_9, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_19, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH /	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.	TOTALLY AGREED).		
Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
information exchanged using SIGRUN.	HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).		
Satisfaction with the operating procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using SIGRUN.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 2 min (120 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the SIGRUN.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 13 June 2023.
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' responders involved in UC3 training actions.
	Description	<p>A survey was carried out with questions (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12) on the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between services. • Extent to which the tested procedure would allow a more efficient execution of assigned tasks in a MCI compared to the current situation. • Opinion on whether this system would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to an MCI • Opinion on the ease and simplicity of implementation by a first responder in a MCI • Opinion on the improvement of the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI • Added value to the management and response in a MCI affecting several communities or countries • Overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged. <p>Degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.</p>
	Execution	<p>As part of the UC working days, a face-to-face training session was held on the operating procedures for responding to an MCI or a disaster using the SIGRUN federated solution (through different federated tools as an example) with a common COP. In this session, the participants practised all the steps and roles involved in the different proposed operating procedures.</p> <p>At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey to gather the opinion of respondents on the usefulness of SIGRUN in improving procedures associated with logistics, deployment and health care by first responders in an MCI or disaster.</p> <p>Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 88,00% (ACHIEVED) 	

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) KPI 4: Implementation ease: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) KPI 5: First responder well-being: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 96,00% (ACHIEVED) KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information exchange facilitation: QUITE IN AGREEMENT Task execution efficiency: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Integration and cooperation: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Implementation ease: QUITE IN AGREEMENT First responder well-being: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Added value in cross-border MCI management: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Satisfaction with information content: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT Satisfaction with the operating procedure: QUITE IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	<p><i>"The interface of the App is terrible for un App in 2023. There should be an animated demo of how to use it. I think there are currently integrated Apps in other countries that serve better. This App looks cheap build. I can hire an indian guy from Fiver and do this for a week under 1000 dollar budget."</i></p> <p><i>"The App and the triage card in the best choice for second triage"</i></p> <p><i>"Problem working due to rain / bad weather in phone use. Barcode scanner better and easier than QR code. Bracelet to have GPC track real time or option to refresh victims position / transfer from one side to another."</i></p> <p><i>"More time to exercise with the App so I feel more comfortable to use it."</i></p>
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 14 June 2023

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

	Participants	Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece), Hellenic National Center for Emergency Assistance – EKAB (Greece), Hellenic Fire Service (Greece), Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (Sofia, Bulgaria), Sandanski Municipality Volunteers Unit (Bulgaria), Military Medical Academy (Bulgaria).
	Description	The objective KPIs relating to the triage time and accuracy using SIGRUN were assessed based on the data recorded in this federated platform during the conduct of the UC3 drill.
	Execution	<p>A double cross-border MCI drill was carried out successively with the participation of different emergency services adopting the roles involved in the emergency response (first responders, disaster managers, technologists, etc.). One of those drills was led by the Greek emergency services and the other by the Bulgarian emergency services, although in both cases the responders from both countries worked together. In the exercise led by the Bulgarian services, the victims were divided into 2 foci: collapsed building and overflowing river. The operating procedures are specifically adapted to the SIGRUN federated system.</p> <p>Each of these roles generated data that were displayed and shared in real time.</p> <p>The demonstration was complemented in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform. SIGRUN was used as the information exchange system federating various technological and software tools used to support responders as example. During the UC, relevant information will be gathered in order to carry out the proposed demonstrations.</p> <p>The identification data and pathology of the drill victims were fictitious.</p> <p>The terminals were previously configured with the associated users. The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN were enabled taking into account GRPD issues.</p> <p>Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform was verified prior to the test.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 10: Time to triage (SIGRUN): 121 sec (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 11: Triage accuracy (SIGRUN): 91,18% (ACHIEVED)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

		<p>The following results were obtained using the procedures in place before the VALKYRIES proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 10: Time to triage: 56,32 sec • KPI 11: Triage accuracy: 88,24% <p>While the SIGRUN-assisted procedure showed slightly higher accuracy than the standard procedure, the poor performance in calculating primary triage times was striking. Unlike the data recorded for the other procedures (manually recorded in real time by the VALKYRIES observers), this data was extracted directly from the SIGRUN database at the end of the exercise.</p> <p>Although the time of completion of primary triage for each victim was clearly recorded in the database, analysis of the stored data revealed that the time at which primary triage began was not recorded. This meant that the primary triage time calculated for each victim included time spent on other tasks, such as moving the first responder from one victim's location to another to continue with the next victim, or even search and rescue actions for some victims.</p>
	History of corrective measures	In view of the characteristics of the sample software tools used in a federated manner in the SIGRUN demonstrators, as well as the complexity of implementing solutions in these tools or in the SIGRUN system in such a short period of time, for the next UC (UC2) the approach to the problem identified with the measurement of the time spent in primary triage was focused on the design of the demonstrator exercise (to reduce the identified confusion factor).
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 15 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC3 drill.
	Description	<p>At the end of the UC3, an extensive online survey was conducted to gather the participants' assessment of various aspects of the exercise, both in relation to the various VALKYRIES enablers brought to the demonstrator, and in relation to the organisation and development of the use case itself.</p> <p>Some of these questions (3, 22, 23, 2.18, 2.3, 6, 21, 2.6) asked about topics such as:</p>

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The potential of SIGRUN to enhance information sharing between services. • The potential improvement in task efficiency during an MCI with the tested procedure compared to existing practices. • Views on the system's capability to promote integration and collaborative efforts with other services and/or procedures during an MCI response. • Feedback on the system's implementation ease and straightforwardness for a first responder in an MCI. • Perception of the system's impact on enhancing the well-being of first responders during MCI operations. • The added benefit to the handling and response of an MCI affecting multiple communities or nations. • Overall contentment with the nature of the information shared. <p>Level of satisfaction with the operating procedures deployed, leveraging the features provided by SIGRUN.</p>
	Execution	<p>This evaluation action was carried out in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform, on the same MCI simulation described for VERIFICATION ACTION #2.</p> <p>In this case, the information taken into account for the evaluation of the enabler was collected through the online survey of those responders involved in the MCI simulation. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 88,3% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 69,8% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 72,1% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 69,8% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 83,7% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 90,7% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 83,7% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 79% (NOT ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p>

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange facilitation: CONSIDERABLY • Task execution efficiency: AGREE • Integration and cooperation: AGREE • Implementation ease: AGREE • First responder well-being: AGREE • Added value in cross-border MCI management: CONSIDERABLY • Satisfaction with information content: STRONGLY AGREE • Satisfaction with the operating procedure: AGREE / STRONGLY AGREE
	History of corrective measures	As discussed above, the subjective KPIs established for the WP5 enablers have compliance criteria such that very positive results (but less than 80% of respondents with a favourable opinion) are considered as non-compliance with the KPI. As these KPIs have been defined in previous stages of the project, they will not be revised at this stage, but will be the subject of lessons learned for other future research projects.
	Lessons learned	As discussed above, the subjective KPIs established for the WP5 enablers have compliance criteria such that very positive results (but less than 80% of respondents with a favourable opinion) are considered as non-compliance with the KPI. As these KPIs have been defined in previous stages of the project, they will not be revised at this stage, but will be the subject of lessons learned for other future research projects.
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 30 – Results sheet CO.WP5-13-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K, section WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 2 and 4 (questions 5 to 12)
- Evidence 5

See Annex C. Results from feedback survey with first responders (Frequency tables), questions 3, 22, 23, 2.18, 2.3, 6, 21 and 2.6.

23.5. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
Description	<p>Initial information sharing during an MCI or disaster is critical to ensuring an efficient and timely emergency response at the outset and as the situation evolves. Standardising early warning procedures ensures that stakeholders receive consistent and straightforward information about the event or risk and the best response steps.</p> <p>VALKYRIES supports the METHANE model, introduced in the UK by JESIP in its "Joint Doctrine: the interoperability framework", as a common approach to the rapid, straightforward and consistent exchange of essential incident data between emergency services in the event of an MCI or disaster. It has been used as a reference for the development of SIGRUN and the integration of the used sample software tools, and has been evaluated in the project demonstrators (UCs).</p> <p><i>M/ETHANE. Joint doctrine: the interoperability framework. Edition 2 July 2016. Pg 9. https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/resources/JESIP-Joint-Doctrine.pdf</i></p> <p>The assessment of this enabler in the UC2 demonstrator was carried out through a questionnaire developed in the UC workdays to collect respondents' opinions on the proposed enabler to sharing initial information regarding the incident when an MCI or disaster is declared (VERIFICATION ACTION #1).</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
effective emergency response.			
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
METHANE UC compliance: The degree of adherence of the incident information shared in the UC to the METHANE model.	%(rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly shared METHANE data by the total METHANE dataset in the UC, expressed as a percentage)	KPI 3: A result of at least 80% of compliance.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Sandanski (Bulgaria), 13 June 2023.	
	Participants	responders involved in UC3 training actions.	
	Description	<p>A survey was carried out containing questions (2 and 3) related to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criticality of the information transmitted in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster to increase the effectiveness of the health response and reduce the risk to responders. • Opinion on whether the information provided is appropriate to the needs of EMS in the early stages of an MCI or disaster. 	

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION	
Execution	During the UC working days, a training session was conducted focusing on the operational procedures for dealing with an MCI or disaster using the integrated SIGRUN solution, exemplified through various federated tools under a shared Common Operating Picture (COP). In this training, participants went through and acted out all the steps and roles associated with the proposed operating procedures. Upon concluding the sessions, each participant from the emergency services involved in the training was asked to complete a questionnaire. This was to gather their feedback to assess whether the METHANE approach was considered appropriate for the initial dissemination of critical incident information. Respondents answered the questionnaire on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.
Analysis and results	The following results were obtained: KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 88,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 92,00% (ACHIEVED) PREDOMINANT RESPONSE: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • Data usefulness: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
History of corrective measures	
Lessons learned	
Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback	
Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 31 – Results sheet CO.WP5-3-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex K, section WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence (evidence 2 and 4, questions 3 and 4)

23.6. WP5 UC3 demonstration evidence

23.6.1. Evidence 1 UC3 WP5: Survey 1

2021 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101017724

VALKYRIES

UC3 Demonstration

- E.WP5-1: VALKYRIES COLLABORATIVE GLOSSARY FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION.
- F.WP5-3: UNIFICATION OF TRIAGE PRIORITY CODING AND TAGGING IN MCI AND DISASTERS AT EU LEVEL
- E.WP5-4: TASSICA 3 STANDARDISED TRIAGE CARD TO ENSURE INTEROPERABILITY, EQUITY, VICTIMS INFORMATION REGISTER AND TRACEABILITY IN MCI AND DISASTERS.

UNIFICATION OF TERMINOLOGY AND CRITERIA IN MCI AND DISASTERS (E.WP5-1, E.WP5-3)

1- Do you think it is important that all emergency services use the same terminology for planning and responding against MCI and disasters?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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2- Do you think it is important that all emergency medical services use the same classification to designate the triage priority of victims in MCI and disasters?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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3- Do you agree with the allocation of colours for the different priorities used in the test?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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4- Do you think that the use of the same classification and colour coding throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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USING A STANDARDISED TRIAGE CARD (E.WP5-4)

5- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card helps to homogenise the triage priorities assigned to victims in an MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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6- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card helps you to decide which life-saving gestures are appropriate for a given victims in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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2021 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101017724

VALKYRIES

7- To what extent do you think the TASSICA triage card helps to ensure the traceability of a victim at the scene of an MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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8- To what extent do you think the TASSICA triage card facilitates the recording of victims' health information in the response to a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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OVERALL ASSESSMENT

9- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card reduces the stress of healthcare personnel in decision-making in the triage of victims in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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10- Do you think that the use of the same standardised triage card throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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11- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card allows you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a MCI compared to other cards?

VERY HIGH	ALTO	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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12- How satisfied are you overall with the TASSICA triage card you have used?

VERY HIGH	ALTO	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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COMMENTS, ASSESSMENTS, SUGGESTIONS:

INSTITUTION: MMA - Sofia
DATE: 11.06.23

Figure 21 – Evidence 1 UC3 WP5: Survey 1

23.6.2. Evidence 2 UC3 WP5: Survey 2

2021 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101017724

VALKYRIES

UC3 Demonstration

- E.WP5-2: EU STRUCTURED REPOSITORY OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS
- E.WP5-5: EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES MINIMUM VICTIM DATA SET (EMS MDS) FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN MCI AND DISASTERS
- E.WP5-7: STANDARDISATION OF BASIC INITIAL ALERTING INFORMATION FOR EMERGENCY SERVICES IN MCI AND DISASTERS IN THE EU.
- E.WP5-6: SIGRUM AS AN INTEGRATION REFERENCE FOR FACILITATING THE DEPLOYMENT AND RESPONSE TASKS OF EMERGENCY SERVICES IN MCI AND DISASTERS IN THE EU.

MINIMUM DATA SET SEM (E.WP5-5)

1- Do you think that the data transmitted in the trial are appropriate for the proper management of victims by an emergency health service in MCI or disasters?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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2- Has the data exchanged helped you to complete your care tasks?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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INITIAL METHANE ALERT (E.WP5-7)

3- Do you believe that the information conveyed in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster is critical to increase the effectiveness of the health response and to reduce the risk to responders?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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4- Do you think that the information conveyed in the initial incident statement text is appropriate for the needs of an emergency service in the first moments of an MCI or disaster?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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VALKYRIES INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCEDURE (E.WP5-2, E.WP5-6)

5- To what extent do you think that the proposed solution could facilitate the exchange of information between the different health services involved in the response to a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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6- To what extent do you think that the tested procedure would allow you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a MCI compared to the current situation?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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2021 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101017724

VALKYRIES

7- Do you think that the tested procedure would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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8- To what extent do you think that the tested procedure is easy and simple to apply by a first responder in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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OVERALL ASSESSMENT

9- Do you think that the proposed solution would significantly improve the well-being of health first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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10- Do you think that the proposed solution could bring added value to the management and response in MCI affecting several communities or several countries?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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11- What is your overall level of satisfaction with the CONTENT (DATA) that has been exchanged in the tested MCI response exercise?

VERY HIGH	ALTO	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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12- What is your overall level of satisfaction with the INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCEDURE that has been tested?

VERY HIGH	ALTO	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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COMMENTS, EVALUATIONS, SUGGESTIONS:

INSTITUTION: Academy of MCI
DATE: 13.06.23

Figure 22 – Evidence 2 UC3 WP5: Survey 2

23.6.4. Evidence 5 UC3 WP5: Victims datasheet

VALKYRIES UC 3. WP5 DATA SHEET. Sandansky 11-15/06/2023.

INCIDENT	ID PAX	1T BENCHMARK	ID SIGRUN	1T SIGRUN	ID USUAL	1T USUAL	1T TIME USUAL	ID TASSICA 3	1T TASSICA 3	TIME 1T TASSICA 3
Earthquake Bulgaria	20	3	TASS0013	3	13	3	22	A230052	3	7
Earthquake Bulgaria	7	2	TASS0027	2	27	2	201	A230022	2	149
Earthquake Bulgaria	3	1	TASS0029	1	73	1	37	A230048	1	71
Earthquake Bulgaria	8	2	TASS0032	2	8	2	50	A230049	2	42
Earthquake Bulgaria	2	1	TASS0037	1	31	1	360	A230059	1	57
Earthquake Bulgaria	22	0	TASS0038	0	22	0	18	A230053	0	25
Earthquake Bulgaria	5	2	TASS0039	2	7	3	90	A230058	3	79
Earthquake Bulgaria	4	1	TASS0042	1	42	1	44	A230164	1	77
Earthquake Bulgaria	24	0	TASS0048	0	24	0	21	A230057	0	22
Earthquake Bulgaria	6	2	TASS0052	3	52	3	52	A230301	3	64
Earthquake Bulgaria	16	3	TASS0053	3	55	3	56	A230060	3	156
Earthquake Bulgaria	23	0	TASS0055	0	23	0	15	A230054	0	30
Earthquake Bulgaria	11	3	TASS0057	3	161	3	93	A230055	3	15
Earthquake Bulgaria	19	3	TASS0058	3	58	3	15	A230162	3	43
Earthquake Bulgaria	12	3	TASS0060	3	60	3	5	A230047	3	40
Earthquake Bulgaria	10	2	TASS0067	3	67	3	19	A230050	2	38
Earthquake Bulgaria	1	1	TASS0072	1	45	1	85	A230024	1	76
Flood	25	2	TASS0006	2	25	2	110	A230081	2	21
Flood	15	3	TASS0049	1	10	2	93	A230163	3	21
Flood	21	0	TASS0056	0	21	0	60	A230036	0	23
Flood	9	2	TASS0068	2	9	2	133	A230112	2	20
Earthquake Greece	8	2	TASS0009	2	9	2	79	A230099	2	49
Earthquake Greece	10	2	TASS0011	2	11	2	9	A230182	2	30
Earthquake Greece	11	3	TASS0015	3	43	3	1	A230184	3	22
Earthquake Greece	5	2	TASS0018	2	18	2	9	A230189	2	60
Earthquake Greece	19	3	TASS0021	3	22	3	34	A230183	3	82
Earthquake Greece	25	3	TASS0022	3	35	3	15	A230181	3	25
Earthquake Greece	12	3	TASS0030	3	36	3	30	A230098	3	27
Earthquake Greece	20	3	TASS0035	3	12	3	30	A230100	3	24
Earthquake Greece	17	3	TASS0036	3	21	3	21	A230318	3	25
Earthquake Greece	7	2	TASS0040	2	40	2	19	A230185	3	26
Earthquake Greece	18	3	TASS0043	3	15	3	15	A230298	3	147
Earthquake Greece	3	1	TASS0046	1	46	1	56	A230190	1	35
Earthquake Greece	1	1	TASS0050	1	50	1	18	A230187	1	21

91,18%	88,24%	56,32352941	91,18%	48,5
ACCURACY	ACCURACY	TIME (sec)	ACCURACY	TIME (sec)

VALKYRIES UC 3. WP5 SIGRUN times estimation.

INCIDENT	Earthquake Bulgaria			INCIDENT	Flood	INCIDENT	Earthquake Greece	
USER	1031	1032	1033	USER	1311	USER	1022	1033
INITIAL TIME	8:05	8:32	8:02	INITIAL TIME	9:48	INITIAL TIME	10:02	9:40
END TIME	8:22	8:35	8:12	END TIME	9:55	END TIME	10:18	9:57
AVERAGE TIME	0:03:24	0:01:30	0:01:40	AVERAGE TIME	0:02:20	AVERAGE TIME	0:01:36	0:01:42
INCIDENT AVERAGE	0:02:11			INCIDENT AVERAGE	0:02:20	INCIDENT AVERAGE	0:01:39	

TOTAL TRIAGE TIME	1:08:27
TOTAL VICTIMS	34
AVERAGE TIME	0:02:01

Figure 24 – Evidence 5 UC3 WP5: Victims datasheet

23.6.5. Evidence 6 UC2 WP5: Triage compliance with VALKYRIES proposal

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Main Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History	Incident	By Unit	By Staff	
TASS0022	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (abdomen/pelvic)	AMBULANCE	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0031	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	F	32 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (abdomen/pelvic)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0016	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0035	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	56 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0018	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	AMBULANCE	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0011	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	17 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0009	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	40 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0040	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	30 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0056	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ELDER	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Flood		HR1 1311
TASS0010	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	20 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1022
TASS0065	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece		P33_BuM 1022
TASS0019	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	23 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck)	AMBULANCE	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0014	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece		P33_BuM 1022
TASS0006	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	28 / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Flood		HR1 1311
TASS0061	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece		P33_BuM 1022
TASS0012	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck)	EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_BuM 1022
TASS0070	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	F	45 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0048	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	17 / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled	TRAUMA	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Flood		HR1 1311
TASS0017	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece		P33_BuM 1022
TASS0062	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed		EMU - AMBULANCE	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0036	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled		EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0050	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	61 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (thorax)	EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0002	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / CHILD	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece		P33_BuM 1022
TASS0030	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0068	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece		P33_BuM 1022
TASS0066	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	20 / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled		EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Flood		HR1 1311
TASS0046	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	21 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (thorax)	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	Municipality of Sandanski	Municipality of Sandanski	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1033
TASS0043	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	F	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Greece	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0021	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0053	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / CHILD	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0057	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0060	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0032	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	60 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck)	EMU - AMBULANCE	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0015	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	60 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck, upper extremity)	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0042	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	F	18 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (thorax, upper extremity)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0067	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / CHILD	Completed	Completed	Completed		PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0063	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0056	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	55 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (upper extremity, lower extremity)	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0038	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0026	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0055	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0048	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1033
TASS0045	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0037	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	25 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck, upper extremity)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	PST_Dr_F 1033
TASS0039	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	F	45 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (head/neck)	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0052	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	F	- / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed		PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	Municipality of Sandanski	Municipality of Sandanski	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	2nd EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1033
TASS0067	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	Cancelled	Cancelled					→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	Monistar escritorio
TASS0072	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	61 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (thorax)	EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0027	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	30 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	EMU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	4th EMBAK - Special Unit for disasters	P33_Dr_F 1031
TASS0029	June 18, 2023, 10:52 a.m.	M	21 / ADULT	Completed	Completed	Completed	TRAUMA (thorax, lower extremity)	EMU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	St. Vlahov HOSPITAL	→	→	Earthquake Bulgaria	CADETE DOCTOR 2 - TRAIE 2 204	

Figure 25 – Evidence 6 UC3 WP5: Triage compliance with VALKYRIES proposal

23.6.6. Images UC3 WP5

Figure 26 – Images UC3 related to WP5

24. Annex L – WP6 Result sheets Opportunities

24.1. CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

24.1.1. CO-WP6-2-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data			
Description	Verify that the data stored in the SIGRUN platform is correctly stored, applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it. Also, the data transmitted over the network is secure.		
Location/Participants	UMU		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T6.1_1		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data stored in the SIGRUN platform is encrypted, as well as data transmitted over the network.	100% of data transferred and stored in the SIGRUN platform is encrypted, except for the cases defined in the premises and limitations	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success) KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications: encryption setting KPI 3: data is stored with in an encrypted format: encryption setting	Analysis
	Description	Data encrypted	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	To carry out this demonstration, SIGRUN has been configured to store encrypted data and to exchange encrypted data over the network, thus ensuring that the data is protected. SIGRUN works by default with https, which means that its exchanges are encrypted, and the database used by SIGRUN has the capacity to encrypt the data so that it remains confidential in the event of an information leak.	
Analysis and results	<i>The results obtained are that the information is 100% available and that the data is exchanged encrypted over the network thanks to https. On the other hand, for the simulations, the option of encrypting the data in the database has been highlighted in order to speed up its operation, but this option can be activated at any time.</i>		

CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	
History of corrective measures	
Lessons learned	<i>We have learned that confidentiality of data is a highly important aspect, especially when dealing with medical issues, which is why data encryption mechanisms have been implemented.</i>
Quality	A
End-user feedback	<i>No end user feedback.</i>
Result	YES

Table 32 – Results sheet CO-WP6-1-T01

24.2. CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.

The demonstrated and tested Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and to integrate them effectively into field operating procedures received very positive feedback from the participants in the UC3. The document clearly defines the essential skills required for volunteers engaged in emergency management operations. The testing confirmed how important it is to develop a standardized training program that incorporates these identified skills to ensure uniform preparedness for volunteers in different emergency situations. It is essential to involve volunteers in field operating procedures by clearly establishing their roles and responsibilities within those procedures.

In addition, the work done in the process of work on this opportunity helps to establish effective channels of communication and coordination between volunteers and the authorities responsible for emergency operations. This will ensure a coordinated response to crisis situations. Finally, it is essential to implement a system for monitoring the skills of volunteers to ensure that they are always ready and efficient in their functions during emergencies.

24.3. CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

The overall results from evaluation of the Joint MCI CIMIC Course is more than positive - very good and excellent rates for relevance of knowledge, logical connection between individual parts, teaching methodology and organization of the course. Some parts of the curriculum, as duration of the course and practical orientation of the knowledge and skills could be put under the consideration. As a whole, very positive appreciation allows to consider that it successfully passes the testing and validation at this stage.

As a result of the discussions, the main characteristics of CIMIC Operational Manual were outlined, such as the content, guidelines and main topics related to practical training, the principles and approaches that should be followed to improve civil-military interaction in natural disasters accompanied by mass casualties. The benefit of such a document at national and European level was confirmed by the participants.

24.4. CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).

The demonstrated and tested Training kit for first responders confirmed the main aim to enhance the work of first responders in case of cross-border MCI by providing knowledge and skills in several key areas. First, awareness of emergency conditions and/or the proper extent of injuries which require first aid. Second, ability to administer appropriate first aid for life threatening injuries (relative to airway, breathing and circulation). Third, evacuation/transport of the victim to medical care facility. Fourth, assist health care providers. Fourth, use of modern digital tools for triage, enhanced situational awareness, data management and protection, communication and information exchange, etc. The most important strength of the training kit is the focus on new technological VALKYRIES solutions, which can greatly facilitate first responders in their operations. The fact is that if first responders are not sufficiently trained to use these technological solutions beforehand, this may result in reluctance and attachment in older and less effective actions.

25. Annex M – Hydrometeorological model of Logodazh River and the Dam

1. Introduction

Catastrophic river floods have increased significantly in recent decades for a number of reasons. One of them is climate change. Other reasons could be dam failure, terrorist acts, etc. According to the UN, between 1995 and 2015, floods affected 2.3 billion people and killed 157,000. According the European Commission Flood Losses in Europe are expected to Increase fivefold by 2050. This requires society to be prepared to deal with such catastrophic events.

The territory under consideration: the Logodazh dam (also known as the Stoykovtzi dam) along with the Chetirka River and the Struma/Strymon River falls in southwestern Bulgaria. The Struma River collects waters from four countries (Republic of Bulgaria, Republic of Serbia, Republic of North Macedonia and Republic of Greece) flowing from north from Bulgaria to south to Greece to the Aegean Sea – see Figure 1. It is a transboundary river known in Greece as Strymon River.

Figure 1. Catchment of the river Struma/Strymon on the territory of 4 countries of the Balkan Peninsula.

Its source is located on the southern slopes of Vitosha mountain, a peak at 2246 m above sea level (m a.s.l.), not far from Sofia. The length of the river is 415.2 km, of which 290 km on Bulgarian territory, the catchment area is about 10,800 km² in Bulgaria (total 17,300 km²) with an average altitude of 900 m a.s.l. The catchment is very elongated. The catchment of the river in Bulgarian territory together with the catchment of the Strumica River in North Macedonia is shown on Fig. 2. Strumica is a right tributary of Struma with a catchment area of 400 km² in Bulgarian territory. The watershed has a distinctly mountainous character with steep slopes and deep valleys. Its eastern part is formed by the highest mountains of the Balkans: Rila (the highest peak of Musala on the Balkan Peninsula 2952 m a.s.l.) and Pirin in the southeast. The western

part is formed by mountains with a lower height - Osogovska, Maleshevska and Ograzhden (1500 - 2000 m). On the BG-GR border it is at 200 m a.s.l. The Struma Basin comprises a range of ecologically valuable and vulnerable ecosystems in national parks, habitat areas and tributaries. It contains substantial water resources, surface and ground (fresh and thermomineral) of strategic importance for the economic development of the territory and the border regions.

Figure 2. Watershed of the Struma/Strymon River on the territory of Bulgaria with tributary Strumeshnitsa.

The climate of the northern part of the basin is of a continental type and gradually changes to a Mediterranean type towards the southern part of the watershed. The average multi-year air temperatures vary from 2.9 °C on the highest peak Musala, in the central part of Rila, to 13.9 °C in Sandanski and Kresna in the south. The annual distribution of monthly average temperatures has a seasonal character with short periods with negative temperatures in the northern and middle parts of the river valley and longer ones in the high mountains – see Figure 3. Temperature also shows a pronounced dependence on altitude.

Figure 3. Annual temperature distribution in three stations with different altitudes (Sandanski 206 m a.s.l., Kustendil 521 m a.s.l., Musala 2925 m a.s.l.).

Annual rainfall totals vary between 500 mm for the plains and 1200 mm for the highland parts of the watershed. For comparison, the average annual amount of precipitation for all Bulgarian territory is 766 mm. Monthly rainfall totals are relatively evenly distributed with a maximum in late spring due to the influence of the continental climate in the north and an increase in early winter due to the Mediterranean influence, which is more pronounced in the southern part of basin. The average monthly precipitation and mean discharge of the Struma in characteristic points of the territory are shown on Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Annual distribution of precipitation (P) at Blagoevgrad and water quantity (Q) at Marino Pole (the last station before the border with Greece).

The present work uses monitoring data from the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) for the periods 1961-1990 and 1991-2020 to include the impact of climate change on precipitation, temperature and runoff. The period 1961-1990 is indicated by the WMO (World Meteorological Organization) as representative one for the calculation of various

statistical characteristics of meteorological parameters. The weather stations in the Struma watershed are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Meteorological stations on Bulgarian territory and their altitude.

No.	Location	H [m]
15601	Kyustendil	520
15611	Blagoevgrad	416
15712	Sandanski	206
61060	Cresna	179
61110	Petrich	132
62050	Dupnitca	555
62060	Rila	505
63010	Pernik	726
61490	Gradevo	466
61640	Kulata	100
61670	Millnik	382
62500	Boboshevo	400
62470	Gueshevo	944
63440	Dolna Melna	928
62480	Rakovo	745
61401	Stanke Isichkovo	700
61475	Belica	832
61480	M, eoe.	1142
61680	Levchnovo	145
61700	Klyuch	500
62410	Kiselitca	949
62440	Dragovishtitsa	510
62540	Rila Monastery	1127
63460	Kalistha	606
63500	Breznik	749
64610	Sturgel	730
64660	Kovachevtsi	988
63070	x. Selimitsa	1305
62520	Bobov Valley	640

The hydrometric stations for monitoring the amount of river runoff, located on the watershed of the Macedonian tributary Strumica, from where the high water flows can be expected are listed in Table 2. The natural annual outflow of Struma on the border with Greece is 2242.47 million m³/year.

Fluctuations of the runoff modulus are quite large in the territory of the basin with minimum values of 1-2 l/s.km² for the low southern parts up to 15-20 l/s.km² for the low mountains in the northwestern part of the watershed and it reaches the high values of 35 – 40 l/s.km² for the high mountains in the eastern part of the basin. These high runoff modulus values are due to high rainfall and little infiltration and evapotranspiration in these parts of the basin. The distribution of river runoff shows a maximum in late spring as a result of large precipitation and snowmelt and a late summer minimum as a result of the small precipitation and large evapotranspiration losses.

Table 2. Hydrometric stations with corresponding catchment areas and average altitudes of the catchments to them.

No. HMS	River	Location	Area, km ²	H _{av.} m a.s.l.
Bulgarian hydrometric stations				
51100	Rechitca	the village of Vaksevo	104	883,25
51150	Ilyina	move on Brichibor	82,2	
51310	Konska	Batanovtci	371,8	805,87
51340	Treklenska	Vranya stena village	515,3	1009,25
51370	Bystrica (Sovolyanska)	village of Garliano	42,2	
51380	Bystrica (Sovolyanska)	Sovoliano village	257,1	1129,05
51390	Novoselska	village of Novo Selo	63,5	
51400	Eleshnitca	village of Rakovo	130	
51410	Eleshnitca	village of Vaksevo	315,2	
51430	German	Dupnitca	454,8	1077,98
51450	Rila	the village of Pastra	222	
51470	Bistrica (Blagoevgradska)	G.D. Slavovo	105	
51480	Bistrica (Blagoevgradska)	Blagoevgrad	206,5	
51490	Gradevska (Elhovska)	Marevo hamlet	59,8	
51500	Gradevska	Gradevo village	180	1222,55
51510	Sushitska	the village of Polena	32	
51520	Vlahinska	Vlahi village	91,6	
51540	Sandanska Bistrica	Lilianovo village	118	
51560	Strumeshnitsa	Zlatarevo hamlet	1580	663,30
51580	Strumeshnitsa	Mitino village	1892	591,03
51650	Struma	Pernik	284	1043,25
51700	Struma	village of Razdavitsa	2171	882,26
51750	Struma	Boboshevo village	4320	891,89
51800	Struma	Krupnik village	6774	944,52
51880	Struma	Marino pole village	10265	910,38
North Macedonian hydrometric stations				
104	Strumica	Novo selo village	1364,4	
103	Strumica	Susevo	466,9	

Logodazh River is a right tributary of Struma. Logodazh Dam (or Stoykovtsi Dam) is 1 km from the village of Logodazh. The catchment of the river with the dam are shown on Fig. 5. It is the largest (artificial) reservoir in the Blagoevgrad region with area of 2.8 km². The maximum depth of the dam is 35 m, and its length is 2.5 km with earthen wall. By type it is categorized as a semi-mountainous dam. It is fed by a diversion channel with a water intake from the Leshnichka River at an elevation of 755 m near the village of Leshko.

In the Logodazh and Struma catchment area, flash floods are generated most often by snowmelt accompanied by rainfall. Analyses show that the most frequently dangerous floods occur when precipitation falls on existing snow cover combined with significant warming. The travel time of high wave from the middle part of the catchment to the Bulgarian-Greek border is less than one day.

Figure 5. The catchment of Logodazh and Chetirka River with the dam.

2. Background

Here we will discuss some products with the help of which the tasks of this project were completed. Hydrologic Engineering Center (HEC) is a division of the Institute for Water Resources (IWR) - U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE). HEC is specialized in the development, documentation, training, and application of hydrologic engineering and hydrologic models – [4]. Some of the HEC products are HEC-GeoHMS – [5], HEC-HMS – [6] and HEC-RAS – [7].

The Geospatial Hydrologic Modeling Extension (HEC-GeoHMS) is a geospatial hydrology toolkit designed to help modeling in HMS software. It uses ArcGIS and the Spatial Analyst extension (products of the Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc. – ESRI) for transforming digital terrain data to a hydrologic data structure. Starting from version HEC-HMS version 4.8 (2021) there is no longer a need to use HEC-GeoHMS when modeling with HEC-HMS. This is due to the fact that HEC-HMS already has enough GIS capabilities and this is the future trend.

The Hydrologic Modeling System (HEC-HMS) – [6] is a software tool for modelling hydrologic processes of dendritic watershed systems. HEC-HMS has a rich set of modeling elements, a large set of hydrological methods, a good user interface and optimization capabilities.

River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) is designed for modelling the following river analysis tasks: Steady flow models, Unsteady flow models, Sediment transport models, Water quality analysis. HEC-RAS allows working with one-dimensional and two-dimensional models – [7].

3. Modelling and Solving

The modelling phase consists of several steps.

3.1 Preparing digital elevation model (DEM) model of the area.

The Logodazh (Stoykovtzi) Dam is located in the river basin of the Logodazh River, which flows into the Struma River near the town of Blagoevgrad. From there, the Struma River continues south and crosses the border with Greece. On the upper area is made digital elevation model – see Fig.6 and Fig.7.

Fig.6. DEM model of Stoykovtzi Dam, Logodazh and Struma River to the border with Greece.

Fig.7. DEM model of Logodazh subbasin.

3.2 Preprocessing of DEM model with HEC-GeoHMS

HEC-GeoHMS is used to process the digital model in a form convenient for use by HEC-HMS. This facilitates the preparation of the actual model in HEC-HMS. For example, river slopes and other features of the spatial model are extracted automatically, which increases the adequacy of the model – see Fig. 8 and Fig 9.

Fig. 8. Preprocessing of DEM model with HEC-GeoHMS (Logodazh subbasin separation from Struma basin).

Fig. 9. Preprocessing of DEM model with HEC-GeoHMS (slopesgrid layer preparation).

3.3. Modelling of the Stoykovtzi Dam, the Logodazh River and the Struma River

Using the modeling elements in HEC-HMS and the processed digital model from HEC-GeoHMS as input data, a model was made in HEC-HMS – Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. Each model element has its own characteristics, settings, and methods for simulating its behavior.

Fig. 10. Preprocessing of DEM model with HEC-GeoHMS (HMS layer preparation).

Fig. 11. HMS sub-model of Logodazh River

3.4. Solving of the model

After completing the schematic model, after loading data and parameters of each sub-model according to its specificity, and after choosing a method to simulate its behavior, the model can be solved – see Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Solving of the model Logodazh dam break.

4. Results

Here we present the results obtained from the simulated catastrophic flood resulting from the Logodazh dam failure and the propagation of the high-water wave along the Chetirka and Struma-Strymon rivers. The areas at risk and prone to river flooding after the city of Blagoevgrad [4] are shown on Fig. 13.

The development of a computer-simulation hydraulic model of catastrophic water wave propagation resulting from the Logodazh dam failure requires an accurate representation of DEM model of the terrain with relevant hydrologic data and also hydrologic inputs used as initial and boundary conditions for full unsteady flow routing.

Fig. 13. Territories of middle Struma at risk of flooding [4].

Real monitoring data of the amount of the rainfall from the meteorological stations on Bulgarian territory of Struma watershed (Table 1) were used and different conditional storm rain scenarios were tested. Additionally, appropriate model parameters for terrain roughness and hydraulic structures must be introduced in order to have confidence in the model results. Relevant coefficients are used to compute overtopping flow. Figure 14 shows the stages of excavation of an earthen wall by overtopping water (as Logodazh dam).

Fig. 14. Example breach process for an overtopping failure.

Model calculations of the propagation of a catastrophic flood high wave resulting from the failure of the Logodazh dam have been carried out. Real terrain data of the Struma-Strymon catchment with corresponding hydrological parameters were entered into the software HEC-GeoHMS, HEC-HMS to calculate the rainfall-runoff process and the water wave propagation. Conditionally high rainfall values were selected over a large area around the Logodazh dam, which would lead to dam breakage from overflow. The date and time of the onset of rainfall followed by an increase until a storm event leading to dam break and subsequent gradual decrease in rainfall were conditionally selected. Representative calculation results are shown in

the Appendix. The inundated area for one flood variant along the length of the Chetirka River from Logodazh dam to the confluence with the Struma River is shown in Figure 15.

Fig. 15. Example of flooded area of Chetirka River.

Of interest is the height of the water wave and its movement down the length of the river. The calculated water wave height and time of arrival at characteristic points down the river to the Greek border for a time period of 48 hours are shown on Fig. 16. A detailed representation of the high wave in more points can be found in the Appendix.

As it can be seen the rainfall starts to increase around 1 o'clock and accordingly the water level at the dam gradually increases until it reaches a maximum value. The peak of the wave at Logodazh dam failure is about 10:45-11:00 o'clock. The peak of the wave near Blagoevgrad is 1 hour later at 12:00 o'clock. Near town of Kresna the water peak is at 13:15-13:30, at the Bulgarian-Greece border is about 15:30. The peak of the wave near Megalochori on the territory of Greece is approximately about an hour and a half later at 17:00. The propagation time of the wave from the Logodazh dam failure to the Bulgarian-Greece border is of the order of 4-4.5 hours and to Kerkini lake it is about of 6-6.5 hours (approximately).

For information, some typical distances are: Logodazh - <Struma river down from Blagoevgrad> --> 11-12 km, Blagoevgrad - <Bulgarian-Greek border (Kulata/Promahonas)> --> 80-83 km and Promahonas - <the lake Kerkini> --> 25 km.

Fig. 16. Calculated water wave height and time of arrival at points along the Struma-Strymon river.

5. Conclusion

Floods are a serious test for people and the life of society as a whole. Their impact can be studied using modern mathematical and software tools.

A simulation model of the consequences of the destruction of the wall of the Logodze dam was made. The occurrence and movement of a high-wave water along the Chetirka and Struma rivers to the Greek border is modelled.

The study shows that the destruction of the dam wall of Logodazh, which is not a large dam and especially when combined with intense rainfall, and taking into account the peculiarities of the semi-mountainous relief, can lead to flooding over a long distance, including on Greek territory.

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